

Classification of Brain Disorder Diseases through Medical Image Processing
using Machine Learning based Data Mining Techniques

By

KANDADAI BHARGAVI

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Under Supervision of

Dr. Nethravathi P S, Professor

Institute of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University

Mukka -574146, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka-574146, Mangalore.

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TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Dr. K Bhargavi, has completed his Research work at Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Hyderabad leading to the award of post-Doctoral fellow Certificate Program in Computer Science and Engineering under the Guidance of Dr. Nethravathi P S, Professor, Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka. on the topic ‘Classification of Brain Disorder Diseases through Medical Image Processing using Machine Learning based Data Mining Techniques’ and further I deem the work fit for the submission as a Research report leading to the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program.

Dean

Institute of Engineering and Technology,
Srinivas University

THE SUPERVISOR REPORT

This is to certify that the Research Report entitled “CLASSIFICATION OF BRAIN DISORDER DISEASES THROUGH MEDICAL IMAGE PROCESSING USING MACHINE LEARNING BASED DATA MINING TECHNIQUES” submitted to Srinivas University, Karnataka, India by K BHARGAVI for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate in Computer Science and Engineering is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Research Report (consist with the Publications) has reached the standard of regulations for the award, and it has not been previously formed for the award of any qualifications or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person.

Dr. Nethravathi P S, Professor
Institute of Engineering and Technology Srinivas
University, Mangalore, Karnataka.

DECLARATION

I, K Bhargavi, (Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar) hereby declare that the research work presented in this form of Research Report is prepared by me based on my publications (which are never submitted for any qualifications) and all the works have been connected to reach the theme of the topic and its interdisciplinary area. The descriptions and narrations found are purely original and authentic. Moreover, I am responsible for all the contents included in the publications and research report.

Hence, once again I declare that the entire work in this research report is original for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar of **Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**.

K BHARGAVI

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Last but not the least; I thank Almighty, who has made my life blissful. May his name be exalted, honored, and glorified.

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INDEX

No. of Content Headings	List of Contents	Page No.
	Title Page	1
	Certificate from Research Centre	2
	Research Supervisor Certificate	3
	Declaration	4
	Acknowledgement	5
1	Research Proposal	7
2	Chapter-1	12
3	Chapter-2	20
4	Chapter-3	34
5	Chapter-4	43
6	Conclusion	72
LIST OF PUBLICATIONS IN CORE AREA		
6	A Survey on Applications and Performance of Deep Convolution Neural Network Architecture for Image Segmentation DOI Number:10.48047/nq.2022.20.22.	
7	Deep Learning Neural Networks for Object Recognition and Contour Tracking-Bases Knowledge Extraction - ISSN 2063-5346 doi: 10.31838/ecb/2023.12.si6.300	
8	IoT Based Smart Grid on Smart Cities- INCECT-22 Virtual Conference paper at Srinivas University, Mangalore	

Research Proposal

Medical image analysis is the science of solving and analyzing medical problems based on different imaging modalities and digital image analysis techniques. Now-a-days in health care industry, the use of direct imaging systems for diagnostic purpose and also digital image processing is becoming very essential.

The X-ray imaging, *Computed Tomography* (CT), *Magnetic Resonance Imaging* (MRI), *Positron Emission Tomography* (PET) and *Ultra Sound imaging* techniques are producing a huge number of digital images which need be processed efficiently, evaluated properly and should be made available to the doctors for their ease of using and getting better results. Availability of various digital image processing techniques makes the entire spectrum of digital image analysis and processing now applicable in the area of medicines. Basically, the image processing covers four main areas of research such as; *image formation*, *image visualization*, *image analysis* and *image management*. Additionally, algorithms for image enhancement can also be added as pre- and post-processing of those research areas.

In order to develop the quality, image processing is performed, which basically analyze and manipulate the digitized images. Through this processing, image is converted into a digital form and some of operations are performed to get the image in enhanced form and simultaneously most useful information can also be extracted from it. In the processing of image, the input is the image, and the output is image or characteristics of image. Image processing follows these three steps: in first step the image is imported into the optical scanner, then in the second step the image is analysed and manipulated, which includes compression of data and enhancement of the image, the third phase covers the result, which may be the image or the report analyzing the image. It is an active field of research, where medical image processing is a very challenging issue. Medical images are the image belongs to human body's inner portions used for medical diagnosis. The study gives emphasis over brain tumours, which is increasing rapidly and damage the healthy cells. Image processing covers *image classification*, *image segmentation* and *image visualization*.

From the extensive literature study in the area of medical image processing, it has been observed that, there is huge need for development of automatic, accurate and validated computational models for image analysis such as, image classification, image segmentation and image visualization. Also, from literatures it is understood that, now-a-days machine learning strategies on image classification played vital role. The Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) are the most widely used methodologies in this field. But while experimenting, it has been found that, in case of ANN, when the inputs are more, the network becomes slow, because the some of the extracted features are correlated and

ANN requires an efficient feature reduction mechanism to overcome the above stated issue. Though, ANN has more layers and becomes complex network, the time to learn the instances, selection or initialization of proper weight becomes the thrust of the research to speed up the training process and in case of SVM, choosing the reduced feature set is a challenge. Therefore, we wanted to explore more on feature reduction techniques before applying any of the above stated machine learning techniques for the development of computational models. Additionally, medical domain for image analysis has been chosen, because the benefit of medical imaging in terms of its ability to yield as accurate diagnosis depends on both the quality of the image and interpretation of the image.

The recent research establishes that, ANN are the most promising approaches for image classification and are best alternatives to different conventional classification methodologies or algorithms. Though, traditional ANNs have advantages, it also suffers from few disadvantages, such as the black box learning approach of ANN cannot interpret the relationship between the input and output and also cannot deal with uncertainties, when the complexities of the system increase, other methods are combined and used for modelling. Recently, *deep learning* which is an advanced form of ANN is doing justice to all the valuable data in almost all the fields of speech recognition, image processing, natural language processing, financial engineering and health care research. It is supervised learning approach for data classification and uses some form of gradient descent mechanism for training the model.

This thesis mail focuses on development three computational models for accurate classification of brain images. Feature extraction is the most crucial pre-processing step for any classification algorithm and the performance of the classifier heavily depend on the numerical properties of various image features which represent the data of the classification model. Therefore, in the first part of the study, an integrated form of Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique (DWT) has been explored and established as a feature extraction strategy to detect the brain disorder from brain MRI images and SVM has been used for classification. Secondly, the design of optimized image classifier plays an important role, therefore, by exploring the capabilities of ELM has been experimented and in the second phase of the work, a hybridized image classification strategy has been proposed based on DWT, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) and ELM named as MABC-ELM. However, traditional machine learning methods are not sufficient to deal with complex problems. Therefore, deep learning methods are trying to resolve the limitations of machine learning based techniques. Deep learning approaches can extract the features from the data automatically to solve the problem of feature extraction through its hierarchical structure. Therefore, an improved Deep Belief Network (DBN) based image classification model has been proposed by combining the DWT for feature extraction and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to get a reduced size of extracted features in the third phase of this thesis.

1. Overview

Medical image analysis is the science of solving and analyzing medical problems based on different imaging modalities and digital image analysis techniques. Now-a-days in health care industry, the use of direct imaging systems for diagnostic purpose and digital image processing is becoming very essential. The X-ray imaging, *Computed Tomography* (CT), *Magnetic Resonance Imaging* (MRI), *Positron Emission Tomography* (PET) and *Ultrasound imaging* techniques are producing a huge number of digital images which need be processed efficiently, evaluated properly, and should be made available to the doctors for their ease of using and getting better results. Availability of various digital image processing techniques makes the entire spectrum of digital image analysis and processing now applicable in the area of medicines. Basically, the image processing covers four main areas of research such as *image formation*, *image visualization*, *image analysis* and *image management*. Additionally, algorithms for image enhancement can also be added as pre- and post-processing of those research areas.

In order to develop the quality, image processing is performed, which basically analyze and manipulate the digitized images. Through this processing, image is converted into a digital form and some of operations are performed to get the image in enhanced form and simultaneously most useful information can also be extracted from it. In the processing of image, the input is the image, and the output is image or characteristics of image. Image processing follows these three steps: in first step the image is imported into the optical scanner, then in the second step the image is analyzed and manipulated, which includes compression of data and enhancement of the image, the third phase covers the result, which may be the image or the report analyzing the image. It is an active field of research, where medical image processing is a very challenging issue. Medical images are the image belongs to human body's inner portions used for medical diagnosis. The study gives emphasis over brain tumors, which is increasing rapidly and damage the healthy cells. Image processing covers *image classification*, *image segmentation* and *image visualization*.

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ANN, when the

inputs are more, the network becomes slow, because some of the extracted features are correlated and ANN requires an efficient feature reduction mechanism to overcome the above stated issue. Though, ANN has more layers and becomes complex network, the time to learn the instances, selection or initialization of proper weight becomes the thrust of the research to speed up the training process and in case of SVM, choosing the reduced feature set is a challenge. Therefore, we wanted to explore more on feature reduction techniques before applying any of the above stated machine learning techniques for the development of computational models. Additionally, medical domain for image analysis has been chosen because the benefit of medical imaging in terms of its ability to yield as accurate diagnosis depends on both the quality of the image and interpretation of the image.

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Therefore, deep learning methods are trying to resolve the limitations of machine learning based techniques. Deep learning approaches can extract the features from the data automatically to solve the problem of feature extraction through its hierarchical structure. Therefore, an improved Deep Belief Network (DBN) based image classification model has been proposed by combining the DWT for feature extraction and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to get a reduced size of extracted features in the third phase of this thesis.

CHAPTER 1

Medical image processing has been expanding its path dramatically and now-a-days this field is also attracting the experts from many other fields of research such as; engineering, mathematics, statistics, biology, computer science etc. Rapid growth in the collection of medical images and their analysis and proper use of those images plays vital role for development of image analysis strategies. Many computational models have been explored and proposed based on magnetic resonance images (MRI), Computed (Axial) Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET). The key benefits of medical imaging are widely used in diagnosing the illness and severity of the disease quickly and accurately and due to this digital diagnostic procedure, the surgery may not be required, which can be characterized by studying the properties obtained using this digital image processing. Considering, the growing interest in the medical image classification, attempts are made in this thesis to focus on design of accurate classification models using MRI, CT and PET images. The development of computational models which can analyse significant volume of images and can produce high quality information out of those images for disease diagnose and treatment is the key focus of this thesis.

Now-a-days in health care industry, the use of direct imaging systems for diagnostic purpose and also digital image processing is becoming very essential. The X-ray imaging, CT, MRI, PET and *Ultrasound imaging* techniques are producing a huge number of digital images which need be processed efficiently, evaluated properly and should be made available to the doctors for their ease of using and getting better results [1-3]. Availability of various digital image processing techniques makes the entire spectrum of digital image analysis and processing now applicable in the area of medicines. Digital image processing basically implemented through three steps i.e. importing images followed by manipulating those imported images and obtaining the results from the above two steps. The key advantages include obtaining the result in reasonable computing time with small interpolation error, consistency and security, ease of diagnosing through cost effective and user-friendly software known as Computer

Aided Design(CAD). Those CAD systems helps to get the scanned copy of the digital images from various sources such as; CT scan, MRI, PET and Ultrasound reports in DICOM format and are prepared for analysis through various phases such as; pre-processing the images by reducing the artifacts, reducing the noise from the images and levelling the quality of images, the it goes through another phase of processing known as segmentation for obtaining the differentiation of differentstructures from the images for finding the region of interest, it's compactness, form, size and location along with proportion of grey levels for proper identification of disease. Finally, after the region of interest has been obtained, images are evaluated and classified with respect to various state-of-the art classifiers.

Figure 1.1 Authored: Steps of image processing

The steps involved in the medical image processing includes the following and also shown in **Figure 1.1**. In the first step, image formation is the process of capturing all the images to construct a matrix for further processing, proper visualization of the image for further processing is the second step, which refers to the manipulation of the resultant matrix, resulting in an optimized output of an image, in the subsequent step, visualization, analysis and proper storage and organization of images are done [3-5] [7-8].

The high level of processing involved in the analysis of biomedical images is inherently apparent due to complex nature of images, difficulty in formulating diagnostic systems. The interpretation of diagnostic images by physicians plays a vital role which plots a gap in the medical domain. Therefore, to bridge this gap, we need to understand the following [5-7] [9-10]:

- a) *Heterogeneity of images*: Complexities associated with medical images which contain the living tissue, organs and body parts. The structures and objects vary from sample to sample even if the images are captures with same modality; therefore, making out priorknowledge and formulation of analysis becomes crucial.
- b) *Unknown delineation of objects*: Medically related terms are mostly abstracted on the texture level, so to understand and comprehend becomes very difficult.
- c) *Robustness of algorithms*: The medical image processing algorithms or models must be able to handle the noise associated with medical images along with the efficiency, quality proposed algorithms must be robust enough to evaluate and compare the proposed algorithm with classic methodologies.

1.2 Problem Statement

The objective of this thesis is to design computational models, which will automatically classify the images with reduced computational complexity and improved accuracy. In this study, the capabilities of machine learning strategies for the development of classifiers are being observed. Basically, SVM, ANN, its variants such; Extreme Learning Machines (ELM) and a new version of ANN i.e. Deep Neural Network (DNN) need to be more explored and experimented with proper validation of models.

1.3 Motivations

From the extensive literature study, it has been observed that, there is huge need for

development of automatic, accurate and validated computational models for image analysis such as, image classification, image segmentation and image visualization. Also, from literatures it is understood that, now-a-days machine learning strategies on image classification played vital role. The SVM and ANN are the most widely used methodologies in this field. But while experimenting, it has been found that, in case of ANN, when the inputs are more, the network becomes slow, because some of the extracted features are correlated and ANN requires an efficient feature reduction mechanism to overcome the above stated issue. Though, ANN has more layers and becomes complex network, the time to learn the instances, selection or initialization of proper weight becomes the thrust of the research to make the training process computationally effective and in case of SVM, choosing the reduced feature set is a challenge. Therefore, we wanted to explore more on feature reduction techniques before applying any of the above stated machine learning techniques for the development of computational models.

1.4 Objectives

The main objectives of this thesis are stated as follows:

- (a) To develop computational models which will automate routine, tedious tasks involved in medical image data analysis.
- (b) Designing a large database for image analysis with subjective values of images is
- (c) difficult to process. Extracting the quantitative values from the images becomes difficult which can be used to perform statistical analysis for the developed computation models. Therefore, we need to focus on this key point while developing any computational model which will take the images as input.
- (d) Those computational image processing models or algorithms can point the radiologists while interpreting images if anytime they miss the things and also must be able to assist them in making difficult choices during investigation.
- (e) To explore the performance of SVM, ANN, ELM and DNN techniques for the detection abnormalities on the medical images.
- (f) To perform thorough study on the state-of-the-art in SVM, ANN, ELM and DNN techniques for classification of brain disorders in medical images.
- (g) To synthesize the theoretical foundations of SVM, ELM and DNN for medical

image classification.

- (h) To implement the above-mentioned algorithms against the widely used methods or models and also to validate those and perform statistical analysis.

1.5 Challenges

To bridge the knowledge in medical imaging, applied mathematics and interventional medical procedures, by developing novel computational and algorithmic methodologies to assist radiologists and surgeons in complex circumstances.

- (a) The medical research program therefore focuses on developing tools for image-guided interventions, to better assist medical professionals in each phase of a patient's care.
- (b) Medical image processing refers to mainly manage and process missing, noisy, ambiguous, inconsistent, redundant, distorted data into a meaningful piece of information which can help the medical practitioners in their clinical practices. Therefore, development of methodology which will be able to select the significant features for accurate classification of images.
- (c) Matching of information or pattern recognition from a medical image involves the matching of extracted features from the image with the previously stored models. Therefore, from the information technology point of view, the development of automatic pattern recognizer or a computational model is highly desirable.

1.6 Broad Scope of the Thesis

Classification of medical images to be diseased or non-diseased is basically done through medical imaging by CT, MRI, PET or Ultrasound reports. Digital image processing of medical images can guide the medical professional for medical interventions such as surgical planning or research purpose. Those image processing models are used by the radiologists, engineers, clinicians to understand the anatomy of the patients [1-7]. The classification models aim at development of new tools for proper visualization and analysis of medical data as shown in **Figure 1.2.**

The objective of this thesis is to develop a computationally effective model which can

collect the data, pre-process them and classify for data analysis and performance evaluation. Here, in this work, an attempt has been made to develop hybridized models based on SVM, ANN and DNN with the objective of feature extraction and image classification.

Figure 1.2 Broad view of biomedical image analysis system

Fig:1.3: Authored

Considering the objectives set for this research work and also to address the challenges identified, necessary steps in image mining such as feature extraction, classification to obtain the meaningful information from brain images, three automatic and optimized classification models with significant features have been proposed.

- (a) Feature extraction is used to obtain the reduced and manageable features from the whole dataset, so that the processing becomes faster and computationally effective. Therefore, in the first phase of this work, a feature extraction model has been put forward based on an integrated form of Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique (DWT) to detect the brain disorder from brain MRI images and SVM has been used for classification validation of this proposed feature extraction model.
- b) Design of optimized image classifier plays an important role. Machine learning strategies are now being used many folds for the design of such classifiers. Therefore, by exploring the capabilities of ELM which is a variant of ANN has been experimented to design an optimized classifier for brain disease images. In this work, DWT, Artificial BeeColony optimizer and ELM classifier are merged to form a novel image classification model for brain MRI images. In the first phase (pre-processing stage), the brain MRI images are decomposed, and features are extracted which has been given as input to the modified ABC (MABC) optimization algorithm which produces the candidate solution from its parent by simple operations from the population. This above process is able to determine the optimal values of the various parameters of ELM such as hidden layer, weights and biases and finally, the training and testing of images based on ELM along with its performance evaluation and validation has been performed in the third phase. The interpretation of medical images is very limited due to its subjectivity, complexities ~~and~~ with the images, variations in the images etc.

However, main technical approach generating for interest in CAD systems in healthcare are mainly focusing on development of computational models based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and best categorized on use of machine learning and soft computing for development of data driven algorithms to mimic the human behavior. While considering the use of machine learning tools for the development of such digital image classification models, it has been studied that, the deep learning-based strategies are more promising instead of traditional machine learning strategies to deal with complex medical problems. Deep learning approaches can extract the features from the data automatically to solve the problem of feature extraction through its hierarchical structure. Therefore, an improved image classification model using deep learning tools has been proposed by combining the DWT for feature extraction and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to get a reduced size of extracted features.

Image classification throws big challenge while dealing with the medical images that to brain images. This is a supervised method based on probability distribution and can be either parametric or non-parametric. Basically, the classification process involves the steps such as; image acquisition, pre-processing, feature extraction, classification and validation or evaluation. The main objective of this work is to design efficient and automatic pattern recognition models for automatic diagnosis of brain image data for better clinical care as well as to review the state of the art methodologies adopted by the research community. Next chapter focuses on various literatures available in this area of image processing basically for classification and segmentation.

CHAPTER-2

Study on Feature Extraction based Image Classification

This section explores the various works done on medical image classification and feature extraction [29-35]. The core concept of feature extraction in this medical image analysis is to provide relevant features from a given medical image leading to development of an accurate image processing/classification model. The literature in the field of feature extraction is flooded using PCA [29-30] to extract the main components, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) [31-32] to extract the discriminant information and similarly Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [32], Factor Analysis (FA) [33] etc. DWT is one of the widely used feature extraction technique and the important characteristics of wavelets such as; irregular and asymmetric is capable of revealing the aspects of data analysis like, trends/ approximation coefficients and discontinuities in higher derivatives/detail coefficients makes the DWT effective for feature extraction [36-40]. In the first work (Chapter 3), we have used the DWT as the core of development of feature extraction model; therefore, detail studies on the use of DWT for feature extraction basically on medical images have been discussed.

Deepak Ranjan Nayak *et al.* [40] proposed a model based on two-dimension DWT and AdaBoost combined with random forest. In this work, authors have used two-dimensional DWT for extraction of features from brain images and then probabilistic PCA has been applied for dimensionality reduction and construction of feature vector and then finally, those features in the form of feature vector has been classified using AdaBoost and random forest classifiers. R. Karthik *et al.* [41] have proposed a multi-scale approach using discrete curvelet transformation for detection of stroke from brain MR images. This discrete curvelet transformation method is based on the multidirectional features for characterizing the brain tissues. This discrete curvelet transformation has been applied to the region of interest at different scales and statistical features such as; mean, skewness, standard deviation etc. and these features are used to construct the relevant and optimal feature set. SVM has been employed to empirically establish the performance of the extracted feature sets. Ayse Demirhan *et al.* [42] proposed a hybridized brain MR image segmentation and feature extraction methodology by combining the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) and Self-Organizing Maps (SOM). This work automatically segments and label the MR images using an unsupervised SOM and Learning Vector Quantization (LVQ). SWT obtains the multiresolution information for distinguishing different tissues in the form of a feature vector,

then SOM is used to segment the images along with LQV for fine tuning the image. This model has been evaluated using Tanimoto similarity index and shows promising result in comparison to the manually segmented images. A hybridized model of DWT and Bayesian NN model for classification of human brain tumor from MRI data has been proposed by Carlos Arizmendi *et al.* [43] and here, DWT has been applied to pre-process the several brain tumor pathologies and the dimensionality reduction by feature extraction from the brain images of MRI has been done using a moving window with variance analysis method or PCA.

Fereidoon Moghaada Nejad *et al.* [44] proposed an optimum feature extraction method based on wavelet-radon transform and dynamic neural network. This work proposes a combined system of feature extraction using wavelet-radon transform and then followed by dynamic neural network for effective pavement analysis and distress classification and authors have also established their model by comparing with static neural network. The accuracy observed by this model is 99%. Recently Manish Sharma *et al.* [45] proposed a strategy to distinguish epileptic seizures based on analytic time-frequency flexible wavelet transform (ATFFWT) and fractal dimension of EEG signals. In this work, the EEG signals are decomposed into sub-bands using ATFFWT and then fractal dimension of those sub-bands are calculated and fed to least square SVM classifier to check the validity of the extracted features and the observed classification accuracy is 100%. A novel brain MRI image classification model based on SVM and neural network has been proposed by Sandeep Chaplot *et al.* [46]. In this classification model, wavelets are considered as the input to the NN self organizing map and SVM and the 94% and 98% accuracy has been observed.

Shradhananda Beura *et al.* [47] used two-dimensional DWT for detection of gray-level occurrence for detection of breast cancer. In this work, authors have generated a feature matrix from two dimensional DWT and those extracted relevant features have been used by Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) and the 98% accuracy has been observed when used with two datasets. An intelligent method of brain image classification by hybridizing the PCA, DWT and BPNN has been proposed by El-Sayed Ahmed El-Dahshan *et al.* [48]. In this model they have hybridized the feature extraction, dimensionality reduction and classification within a single model and the obtained accuracy is 97% to 98%. A multi-modal image fusion method based on Discrete Fractional Wavelet Transform (DFRWT) has been proposed by Xiaojun Xu *et al.* [49]. In this method, the correlation between sub-band coefficients are fused with weighted regional variance rule and finally the DFRWT has been used to get the fused image for analysis and the effectiveness has been tested with mutual information and standard

deviation. M. Saritha *et al.* [50] proposed a brain image classification model by integrating the wavelet entropy and probabilistic neural network, here, authors have used wavelet entropy for feature extraction and based on spider web plots and probabilistic neural network for classification and it has been found that, this probabilistic model combined with DWT addresses 100% accuracy. A wavelet-based morphometry model has been proposed by Erick Jorge Canales-Rodriguez *et al.* [51]. This wavelet-based morphometry has been evaluated on gray image matters and based on voxel-based morphometry style analysis.

Sudeb Das *et al.* [52] proposed a brain image classification model based on multi-scale resolution analysis tool for digital images. The PCA has been used for reduction of dimensionality of the feature vector for the images. Authors have used least square-SVM (LS- SVM) to classify the brain MR images. The added benefit of their proposed model is as authors are using ripple transform, and it can capture 2D singularities in different curves in any direction, it provides better image representation. Y. Zhang *et al.* [53] proposed a novel method for MRI brain image classification using adaptive chaotic Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). They have used Feed Forward Neural Network (FNN) to classify MRI brain images. The observed accuracy of the proposed method is 98.75%. This proposed method used transform to extract features from images, and PCA to reduce the dimensions of features and then finally the reduced features are sent to an FNN, and these parameters are optimized via adaptive chaotic particle swarm optimization.

E.A. El-Dahshan *et al.* [54] presented a survey work on computer aided diagnosis system for human brain tumor through MRI. In this system, a feedback pulse-coupled neural network for image segmentation, DWT for feature extraction and PCA for feature reduction has been used. The feed forward back-propagation neural network has been used to classify the resultant images. The classification accuracy observed for test images is 99%. Similarly, S. Wang *et al.* [55] proposed a PSO and artificial bee colony based hybridized feed forward neural network model for abnormal brain detection. For feature extraction from brain images, this methodology used stationary wavelet transform, and then PCA has been used to reduce the dimension. The observed accuracy of this model is sensitivity of 99.37%, average specificity of 100.00%, average precision of 100.00%, and average accuracy of 99.45%.

Image Classification based on non-deep based strategies.

Tawseef Ayoub Shaikh and Rashid Ali [56] developed an automated tissue segmentation and classification using DWT, Band Expansion Process (BEP), Kernel-based least squares Support Vector Machine (KLS-SVM) tools. They have used structural MRI images for experimentation. A novel segmentation method for MR brain images using of Independent Component Analysis(ICA) with a generalized version of the popular Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) has been proposed by Megha Maria Cheriyan *et al.* [57]. Authors try to optimize the parameters of mixture model using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to escape the problem of local traps (maxima or minima). The experiments were carried out using MR Brainweb image sets.

Mahmoud Khaled Abd-Ellah *et al.* [58] reviewed the practical implications and key achievements of designing CAD systems for brain MRI images. They studied the diagnosis system considering the traditional machine learning approaches as well as deep learning techniques. Authors have observed the differences and similarities among those techniques for MR images and also given few possible future directions. Mohammad Khatami *et al.* [59] presented a feature extraction approach known as BundleMAP to extract features from dMRI datasets which uses classification, regression and hypothesis testing. They have tried to combine the outlier removal and feature selection approach to develop this proposed technique.

Ruey-Maw Chen *et al.* [60] applied an optimized extenics based approach to classify the brain MRI images. In this approach, standard deviation is used to select the centroid of the extenics based correlation function and then optimized with PSO. An entropy-based segmentation and classification model of brain MR images has been proposed by V. Rajinikanth *et al.* [61]. Authors tried to enhance and extract tumor core edema sector from MRI and it has been integrated using Teaching Learning Based Optimization (TLBO), entropy value, and levelset / active contour-based segmentation.

A Ratna Raju *et al.* [62] proposed a segmentation and classification algorithm for braintumor datasets named as HCS abased multi SVNN applying the Harmony-Crow Search upon SVNN classifier to train the machine. Additionally, this algorithm determines the level of tumor on brain studying the features of segments originated from Bayesian fuzzy classifier.

Yong Xia *et al.* [63] used Bayes inference and local variational Gaussian mixture models for brain MRI for classification and segmentation. Authors tried to learn a cohort of proposed model on sampled data elements. They have experimented and validated their model on clinical MRI image datasets as well as synthetically created datasets. Peifang Guo [64] did an exhaustive study on brain tissue classification and segmentation for CAD systems. Authors tried to propose a method for joint tissue segmentation for brain MRI datasets. Additionally, tried to obtain non-brain tissue before segmentation and then performs post-processing, iterative contour refinement and morphological reconstructions.

Saima Rathore *et al.* [65] reviewed many articles on neuroimaging classification and feature extraction techniques basically for Alzheimer's disease. Their study mainly focused on structural MRI, reduced density map feature-based methods, supervised/unsupervised feature-reduction-based methods, atlas-based methods, cortical surface-based, reduced vertices as features-based methods, atlas-based methods, Pre-defined regions-based methods, hippocampal features, biologically selected features etc. Iván Cabria and Iker Gondra [66] used the ensemble approach to achieve fused segmentation of brain MRI datasets. They tried to integrate the results obtained by Potential Field Clustering and other methods to design an ensemble technique. Authors tried to use the concepts of potential fields of physics and intensity of pixels in MR images are studied as mass to generate this potential field and clustering approach based on this has been implemented to segment and classify the image datasets.

A Tolerance Rough Set Firefly based Quick Reduct approach has been proposed by Jothi G. and Hannah Inbarani H [67] by exploring the rough set and firefly optimization techniques. Authors tried to collect different categories of features from brain MRI based on shape, intensity and texture etc. Tolerance rough set is applied to obtain the reduct from the datasets and this proposed approach had been compared with few other techniques such as; Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), Cuckoo Search Algorithm (CSA), Supervised Tolerance Rough Set-PSO based Relative Reduct (STRSPSO-RR) and Supervised Tolerance Rough Set-PSO based Quick Reduct (STRSPSO-QR) etc. Sayan Kahali *et al.* [68] presented a two-stage fuzzy multiobjective framework (2sFMoF) method for segmentation and classification. First, they

applied 3D spatial fuzzy c-means (3DSpFCM) along with 3D spatial neighborhood information method obtain the local and global membership function; the clusters are obtained and given to 3D modified fuzzy c-means (3DMFCM) algorithm to generate the final product. This model has been validated through several synthetic datasets.

A review on segmentation and classification strategies for MRI datasets is proposed by Geethu Mohan and M. Monica Subashini [69]. Authors presented current trends in segmentation and classification of brain MRI datasets. Rupali S. Kamathe and Kalyani R. Joshi [70] proposed an integrated image classification model named BEP + ICA+ Thresholding + 'SVM trained with Grey Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). Authors tried to judge the effectiveness of independent component analysis to get the segmented tissue which is basically used for atrophy detection. Wadhah Ayadi *et al.* [71] explored the benefits of DWT and Bag-of-Words (BoW) for classification of brain MRI datasets. The experiments were performed on 256×256 images of DS-66, DS-160 and DS-255 datasets from Harvard Medical School. Similarly, Bashayer Fouad Marghalani, Muhammad Arif [72] presented an algorithm for detection and classification of brain pathologies using bag-of-features methodologies from tumors and Alzheimer diseases. A comparison based on classification of MRI datasets has been introduced by N. Sauwen *et al.* [73]. In this work, authors tried compare on segmentation and classification models for cMRI, DWI, MRSI and PWI datasets.

DNN based Image Classification

The advantages of deep learning in comparison to traditional ANN will not only help to select and extract the significant features but also it makes easier to construct new ones from the existing features [74-76]. This section explores the research carried out for image classification based on deep learning strategies.

Carlos Affonso *et al.* [77] used the deep learning for classification of images on wood boards and compared the proposed method with decision tree, ANN, *k*-nearest neighbour and SVMs and achieved superior performance over those traditional classifiers. Authors suggested that, because of complex structure, deep learning needs a large volume of data to generate models with better predictive performance and also it shows high computational costs, therefore, use Convolution Neural Network (CNN) is a better choice for training the network over traditional classifiers. For better management and querying of large image databases

which needs content-based image retrieval systems Adnan Qayyum *et al.* [74] proposed a image retrieval system based on deep CNN. Authors proposed two strategies for image retrieval, first; by obtaining the prediction about the class of query image by the trained network and then search the queried image in that specific class only. Second one focuses on retrieving the image from the whole database without considering the class information. A survey work has been done by Geert Litjen *et al.* [77] reviews deep learning concepts for medical image analysis. The survey basically focuses on image classification, image segmentation, object detection and registration etc.

Amin Khatami *et al.* [78] proposed an image classification method using DWT and DBN in a three step framework for radiography images. In the first step, they have used DWT for de noising and extracting irrelevant images, in the second step DBN has been used for learning the unlabelled features and finally, in the third step, the features obtained from first and second step has been fed to the classifiers. Similarly, a fused deep learning-based classification for image datasets has been proposed by Xiaohong Gao *et al.* [79]. Authors tried to use the capabilities of CNN and observed 92% accuracy in terms proper classification of brain MRI. A deep learning-based strategy for Alzheimer disease classification has been proposed by Xiaohong W. Ga *et al.* [80].

Harshita Sharma *et al.* [81] explored the deep learning methods in histological image analysis. CNN has been used for cancer classification and approach has been compared with traditional image analysis methods and also the statistical measures have been focused to validate the methodology. M.M. Al Rahhal *et al.* [82] also explored the learning mechanism of deep learning network for electrocardiogram signals. They have used stacked auto-encoders with sparsity constraint to learn the suitable features and after this a softmax regression layer on the top of deep neural network has been added. Qiling Tang *et al.* [83] proposed a multi-scale representation learning method using sparse auto-encoder networks to capture the images and their intrinsic scales for classification. Fisher vector techniques have been proposed to encode the extracted feature which provides more descriptive and discriminative features for the representation. Ping Zhong *et al.* [84] proposed DBN to deal with the problem of image classification. DBNs generally, first do unsupervised pre-training of unlabelled data and then opt for supervised fine tuning over labelled data samples. Authors proposed method has been efficiently implemented under the recursive greedy and back propagation learning algorithm.

A review on importance of deep learning for infant MRI datasets has been done by Mahmoud Mostapha, Martin Styner [85]. Authors tried to compare and review various challenges and issues related to low data size, imbalance data elements, non-ability of interpreting the datasets of MR images. Another review on impact of deep learning on image segmentation and classification has been done by Ali Işın *et al.* [86]. Their focus was to study the recent deep learning methods applied on design CAD systems. Alexander Selvikvåg Lundervold and Arvid Lundervold [87] provided a short review on deep learning methodologies for MRI datasets. Authors focussed on MRI processing, image retrieval, segmentation, classification, and visualization. Muhammed Talo *et al.* [88] developed a deep transfer-based learning approach for brain MRI data classification. They have also addressed the data augmentation, optimal learning rate and fine tuning of their proposed model.

Deep CNN for Image Classification

Dividing an image into several meaningful structures or constituent regions or objects is known as *image segmentation*. This is basically an important pre-processing step for image analysis which leads to object representation, detection, recognition, measurement, and visualization and while partitioning an image into several distinct regions care should be taken to extract the objects or features of interest that correlate strongly [26-28]. Therefore, segmentation is also known as a mechanism of grouping pixels those shares similar attributes. Study reveals various kinds of image segmentation mechanisms. This image segmentation helps to process the low-level images to high-level ones. The success of image analysis is often based on success or failure of image segmentation.

But designing an accurate and reliable segmentation mechanism for image segmentation is thrust area for many of applications. The stopping criterion for image segmentation is when there is no object of interest with respect to the application is available. To separate an image into coherent groups or regions there are many traditional methods such as point, line, edge detection, thresholding, regions growing and morphological watershed and also few advanced methods such as clustering, model fitting and probabilistic methods are now under study [89-90]. Further, the categorization of image segmentation can be broadly classified into (a) *thresholding-based segmentation*; (b) *edge-based segmentation*; (c) *region-*

based segmentation; (d) *clustering technique* and (e) *matching* [24-28]. Image segmentation algorithms are basically based on discontinuity and similarity. The discontinuity-based approach, partitions the image based on the abrupt changes in the intensity of the images and similarity-based approach, partitions the image based on the similar type of regions based on some criteria such as thresholding, region growing, region splitting and merging [91]. This section focuses on a thorough study on the medical image segmentation using a new variant of neural network called deep neural network or CNN and here, we have focused on only the application of Deep CNN and its performance in image segmentation from literatures available during 2016 to 2019 only.

Studies on image segmentation for bio-medical datasets

Studies shows the importance of image segmentation in the field of bio-medical data analysis and has played an important role for automated detection of cancerous cells from mammographic images, CT, MR, PET and Ultra sound images etc. [26-28]. Most medical images have poor noise-to-signal ratio than pictures taken in digital camera which leads to low spatial resolution and decreases the computational reliability. For example, the case of ultrasonic images, speckle noise reduces the ability of taking final decision in medical data analysis. Therefore, to obtain a clear image for proper verification and analysis from an image requires being pre-processed and this is called as *image segmentation*, in which we try to obtain the segments from the images in the form of pixels and the information gained from two image can be used to get proper integration of useful data from the image of interest [91]. CAD systems are used to assist the clinicians, researchers, and physicians in many ways such as, reducing the manual errors, getting better scope to analyze the data in reduced time etc.

Therefore, there is a thrust in design of CAD systems which will give better scope for segmentation and classification. The representation of brain images, segmentation, pre-processing and classification are required for noise reduction, enhancement of image quality and clarity and this image segmentation as a pre-processing task becomes the essential task and further analysis many machine learning based techniques such as, *k-mean*, *k-medoids*, hierarchical and density based clustering techniques as well as artificial neural network with its many variants played a very significant role.

Along with traditional neural network, recently many image segmentation works for medical image analysis has been done with promising results with respect to its computability and accuracy [92-93].

Deep-CNN and its application for image segmentation

CNN proves outstanding performance in many of the areas, basically in medical data image [94-98], it carefully classifies the suspect area in the diagnostic process of the second phase. In fact, it is able to detect all most all disease patterns. Recently, the focus of ANN researchers has been shifted to deep learning, which is a class of ANN computing models, and it learns from a hierarchy of high-level features built from the lower-level ones. These types of models are also known as CNN which automates the process of feature construction and involves both linear and on-linear data to learn and build the automated model from high level information from the low-level information [99-114]. Considering the computational capabilities of CNN, Xiaohong W. Gao *et al.* [99] proposed a non-supervised automatic model to classify CT brain images for diagnosing it into having Alzheimer’s disease or not. Three classes of CT images were first clustered into AD, lesion (tumour) and normal and this model has reported the accuracy of 85.2%, 80% and 95.3% for the above mentioned three classes with an average accuracy of 87.6%. Another fused work on deep learning by Xiaohong W. Gao *et al.* [100] for classification of echocardiography has been proposed recently. They have proposed one hybridized network architecture with two CNNs along space and time directions to learn spatial information and pre-processing of the all the images are done in temporal CNN before trading/learning starts and finally, to get the velocity and acceleration of images, the optical flow has been applied twotimes.

Figure 2.1 Reference:- Cecilia S. Lee *et al.* [102] - Structure of CNN

A deep-CNN based model for image classification has been proposed by Shuchao Pang *et al.* [101]. The proposed domain transferred Deep-CNN (DT-DCNN) showed significant increase in the accuracy while classifying the medical images with high precision. The new thought of the authors for simple data augmentation based on classification has improved the performance of this CNN based hybridised model. A report on deep CNN and machine learning methodologies has been reported by Cecilia S. Lee *et al.* [102] for automatic image analysis from electronic medical records. Authors explored the capabilities of deep learning to distinguish normal and diseased MRI images. A new convolutional neural network for classification with weights initialized by Xavier algorithm has been proposed. The performance of the deep neural network model has been recorded on 500 iterations using cross validation with validation test. This network has identified the key areas of the optical coherence tomography images and the testing can identify the potential features to distinguish AMD images from normal images.

Wei Shen *et al.* [103] investigated the classification of CT images using machine learning based architecture and coined as Multi-crop Convolutional Neural Network (MC-CNN) to automatically extract the suspicious information based on an multi-crop pooling strategy which crops different regions from convolutional feature maps without using segmentation to produce multi-scale features and applied on computationally effective single network. An interesting work on breast cancer diagnosis in mammography using deep learning strategy has been proposed by John Arevalo *et al.* [104] which automatically mine the discriminative features for learning. The proposed deep learning model is based on two phases, first the quality of image is enhanced by preprocessing the images and in second phase, a supervised training strategy has been employed to classify the images. In the pre-processing stage, the images are cropped, then it goes through data augmentation, global contrast and local contrast normalization and then the machine learns the discriminative features using deep learning-based strategy or CNN. Automatic tumor segmentation of CT images is also one the challenging issue observed by the researchers, because the tumors have large spatial and structural variability. To address this issue a recent work for CT image segmentation using multiple supervised fully CNN by Lin Huang *et al.* [105] has been proposed. This model also goes through two phases, consisting of pre-processing to lower the

differences among the images and a three-layer multi-scale feature learning approach to obtain both local and global images. The pre-processing has been performed in two aspects such as image intensity normalization and to find the area of interest of that image.

A CNN based multi-grain classification model for tumor has been proposed by Muhammad Sajjad *et al.* [106]. Authors have tried to use deep learning to segment the MRI datasets and then augmentation on this dataset is done for multi-grain brain tumor data classification. The tumors can appear anywhere in the brain and can be of any kind, size, shape and contrast. Therefore, to address the segmentation of this brain images, recently machine learning techniques are being explored very well. Considering the capability of deep neural network or CNN Mohammad Havaei *et al.* [107] proposed a novel CNN architecture which exploits both local and global contextual features. Rather than a traditional CNN, they have used a final layer in a convolutional network. Their model works in two phase training process to handle the imbalance of tumor class labels. The proposed two-path architecture goes through two phase training procedure which better deals with label imbalance problem of data distributions.

This proposed cascade architecture is efficient, and its performance has been measured by DICE, sensitivity and specificity. A deep-CNN based model for MRI classification has been addressed by Wenlu Zhang *et al.* [108] to study the development in health and disease. Authors have proposed a deep CNN strategy to segment the isointense stage brain tissue based on a fully trained model. CNN with many hidden layers have been proposed and all the patches extracted have been studied and it has been found that patch from each extracted tissue is not balanced. Deep-CNN also plays an important role in Forensic Dentistry also, Yuma Mikia *et al.* studied a deep-CNN model for identification of dental problems in [109] such results are used to record the dental data properly. First, they have mined the regions of interest from CT images and those were used for training this network. Basically, authors have investigated the power of random sampling for both training and testing. The initial hand cropped region of interest has different sizes, but for experimentation, those images were again automatically resized and randomly cropped, and the result have been compared with four resizing mechanisms.

The classification accuracy observed using data augmentation is 93.5%. Pavle Prentašić *et al.* [110] used this Deep-CNN to study the complications of diabetics caused by diabetic retinopathy. Before using the Deep-CNN, a denoising technique called *total variation* has been applied on the fundus photographs to exclude noise levels.

Jun Xu *et al.* [111] worked on automatic Deep-CNN based feature learning algorithm for segmentation and classification of tissues in histological images. The Deep-CNN strategy proposed in this study consists of two alternating convolution layers, maxpooling, two connection layers and a final classification layer. To train this network, coarse-to-fine sweep approach has been applied to extract more fine-tuned settings. LIBSVM (a class of SVM classifier) with *Gaussian Kernel* has been used. The proposed model has been compared with nine state of the art Deep-CNN based models and also the sensitivity analysis and AUC curves are used to establish the performance of the model. Xipeng Pana *et al.* [112] worked on the Deep-CNN for segmentation of nuclei in pathological images. This work progresses in three phases; first sparse reconstruction has been used to remove the background from pathological reports, then in second phase; Deep-CNN with cascade of convolution networks trained with gradient descent has been applied for segmentation of cell nuclei from the background. The machine has been trained with input patches with their corresponding class labels from the randomly selected pathological images.

This model has also been compared with existing few existing methodologies such as; SVM, k -NN and k -means. Recently, a deep CNN named as Deep NAT has been for automatic segmentation of the neuro-anatomy in T1-weighted magnetic resonance images has been proposed by Christian Wachinger *et al.* [113]. This proposed multitasking model not only predicts the center voxel of the batch but also considers neighbors. This study also addresses the mostly challenged class imbalance problem by arranging two hierarchical networks to separate foreground from the background and identifies brain structures on the foreground.

Summary

Automatic segmentation of CT images, ultrasonic videos images of echocardiography, OCT images, brain tumor for cancer diagnosis is a challenging task for the computer scientist. There are many publicly available datasets are provided for the researchers to experiment, develop and evaluate their proposed models for image segmentation. This chapter initially sketches the basic concepts of medical image processing. We have specifically tried to understand the Deep-CNN and its applications in image segmentation for medical images only and also our focus is only the recent work done in this field from 2015 to 2019. Medical image

processing has a significant growth in development of new technologies and still a lot research is left unattended and will definitely encourage the researchers to explore new technologies for proper identification, detection, diagnosis and exploration of images for medical field.

CHAPTER 3:

Methodologies Adopted for Experimentation- *Discrete wavelets transform* (DWT). DWT is a dimensionality reduction technique, which transforms image pixels to discrete wavelet representation. It is described mathematically as a set of dot products between, finite length sequence and a discretized sequence basis [36]. The result of each dot product is a wavelet transform coefficient. It can be mathematically expressed as in

$$Wf(j, k) = \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} f(x) \cdot \varphi_{j,k}^*(x) \quad (3.1)$$

Where, $Wf(j, k)$ is a DWT coefficient and $f(x)$ is a sequence with length N . The

expression $\varphi_{j,k}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s^j}} \psi\left(\frac{x - ks}{s^j}\right)$ is the discretized wavelet basis, where s^j is the discretized

In the case of Haar, mother wavelet high-pass and low-pass filters have length two whereas, for higher other Daubechies, the maximum scale M can be much lower. Comparing with Gaussian and Laplacian pyramid multi-scale representation, DWT produces non redundant image representation, providing better spatial and spectral localization of image formation [37]. *Haar* wavelet transform is a simplest type of wavelet, which [38] pair up input values and passes the sum and store the differences. This process is recursively repeated to provide the next scale by pairing up the sum. It is a simple form of compression storing detail coefficients, such that the initial matrix is similar to the resulting matrix. The Daubechies wavelet transforms is defined in the similar way as *Haar* wavelet transform, where the running average and differences are computed by scalar products with scaling signals and wavelets.

At any level, DWT is having available [39] decomposition as well as similarity of data structure with respect to resolution. SVM and its kernel functions. SVM is categorized under supervised learning strategy and is best used for classification, regression and also detection of outliers. The effectiveness in high dimensional spaces, especially, when the number of dimensions are larger than the number of samples, this SVM shows good performance. It uses a subset of training points known as support vectors in the decision function to obtain the decision line for separation. There are various kernel functions available to obtain the decision line when the data is non-linear.

But when the numbers of features are more than the number of samples over fitting may occur and this can be avoided using kernel functions and the challenge is to choose the appropriate kernel function. Additionally, SVMs use an expensive method of five-fold-cross validation strategy to provide the probability estimates [126-128]. The working principle of SVM tries to find a decision line or separating surface which can be linear or nonlinear for the data space. Given a training set with label pairs (u_i, y_i) , $i = 1, \dots, n$ where $u_i \in \mathcal{R}^n$ and, $y \in \{profit, loss\}^i$, SVM requires solution of the following optimization problem (3.2).

$$\min_{w, b, \xi} w^T \bar{w} + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i$$

Subject to: $y_i(w^T \Phi(u_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \xi_i \geq 0$. Where, decision function is given by (3.3).

$$p = \text{sgn}(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i K(x_i, x) + \rho) \quad (3.3)$$

The non-linearity can be solved using kernel functions such as; $k(u_i, u_j) \equiv \Phi(u_i)^T \Phi(u_j)$.

SVM can be trained using various kernel functions as detailed in (3.4), (3.5) and (3.6).

$$(a) \text{ Linear kernel: } k(u_i, u_j) = u_i^T u_j, \quad (3.4)$$

$$(b) \text{ Polynomial kernel: } k(u_i, u_j) = (\gamma u_i^T u_j + r)^d, \gamma > 0, \text{ and } \quad (3.5)$$

$$(c) \text{ Radial Basis kernel (RBF): } k(u_i, u_j) = \exp(-\gamma \|u_i - u_j\|^2), \gamma > 0. \quad (3.6)$$

The kernel parameters in those equations depends on the datasets and we need to choose the kernel parameter properly otherwise, it can be affected by the training set size.

Performance evaluation measures

For validation of the proposed model, various validation measures based on classification accuracy have been used and are discussed here. A confusion matrix has been created to measure the classification accuracy and based on this matrix, True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), False Negatives (FN) and True Negatives (TN) Sensitivity or recall, Precision, the F1- score are computed and used for evaluation.

Schematic Layout of Proposed IDWT Image Classification Model

A feature extraction technique based on IDWT has been proposed. The datasets used for the experimentation have been supported and maintained by Harvard’s University (<http://www.med.harvard.edu/AANLIB>). It provides various brain image datasets for different diseases along with normal brain image. The images have been collected in *gif* format in grey scale with size 256×256 each. The main objective of feature extraction from brain images is to automatically classify any brain disorder disease from a well specified and well-organized classifier model. The features can be extracted by using different techniques. Here, a well- defined and an efficient feature extraction from brain images using an integrated wavelet approach has been explored. The detailed architecture has been specified in **Figure 3.1**.

Figure 3.1 Authored : Architecture of proposed IDWT model for feature extraction and classification of brain images

In this method first of all the several brain images from the above reference are collected and all are in *transaxial plane*. Other than this there are other types of plane are available such as *sagittal* and *coronal*. These are the different orientations of the human brain through which the images are collected. In this chapter, only the images in *transaxial plane* have been considered for experimentation. After the images are collected an IDWT technique for feature extraction has been proposed. Generally, DWT is considered as the most efficient technique for feature extraction from images in a two-dimensional space. The core part of

DWT is the mother wavelet function used for transformation. There are different functions available such as *Daubechies*, *Haar*, *Morlet*, *Coiflet*, *Bi-orthogonal 1.x* etc. [38-39].

In this work, an IDWT technique have been explored and experimented for feature extraction from brain images combining the advantages of *Haar* and *Bi-orthogonal 1.3* wavelet. After features have been extracted from two different integrated wavelet functions, then the entire combined feature matrix has been provided to a classifier model that is SVM with *linear kernel* to classify different brain disorder diseases. The experimental evaluation described in the next section confirms that proposed IDWT outperforms on other single wavelet functions. Also we have compared the performance of SVM classifier with other classification techniques suchas *MLPNN*, *Gaussian NB* and *Logistic Regression*.

Experimentation and Model Evaluation

Wavelet transform is a very powerful tool for feature extraction from images as well as non-stationary signals. DWT is generally considered as the most efficient technique for image decomposition and feature extraction. This is mainly popular because it analyzes signal or image at different scales of resolution, and it is useful for detailed analysis of images. In this work, two wavelet functions such as; orthogonal wavelet function *Haar* and is *Bi-orthogonal 1.3* wavelet function have been used extensively. The mother wavelet function for Haar can be defined as given in (3.7) and the scaling function can be defined as shown in (3.8).

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq x < 1/2 \\ -1 & 1/2 \leq x < 1 \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\phi(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq x < 1 \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

Other type of wavelet function used in this work is Bi-orthogonal in which the wavelet function is not necessarily orthogonal but it is invertible. In this case two scaling functions ($\phi(x)$) as given in (3.9) and (3.10) are used which are associated with two different wavelet functions ($\psi(x)$) of (3.11) and (3.12).

$$\phi(x) = 2 \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} h(n)\phi(2x - n) \tag{3.9}$$

$$\tilde{\phi}(x) = 2 \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{h}(n)\tilde{\phi}(2x - n) \tag{3.10}$$

$$\psi(x) = 2 \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} g(n)\phi(2x - n) \tag{3.11}$$

$$\tilde{\psi}(x) = 2 \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{g}(n)\tilde{\phi}(2x - n) \tag{3.12}$$

Due to this property of bi-orthogonal wavelet it may generate different multi-resolution analyses. In this work, we have not just considered only the regular wavelet functions, rather an integrated version of these two wavelet functions. The integration of the functions is calculated separately using rectangular integration method as shown in (3.13).

$$\int_{x=-\infty}^t \psi(x); \text{ for Haar wavelet function and } \int_{x=-\infty}^t \tilde{\psi}(x) \text{ for Bi-orthogonal wavelet}$$

Figure 3.2 Authored: DWT based feature extraction from normal (a) and Alzheimer (b) brain imaging using integrated Haar wavelet function

Figure 3.3 Authored: DWT based feature extraction from normal (a) and Alzheimer (b) brain imaging using integrated Bi-orthogonal 1.3 wavelet functions

Since, Haar is an orthogonal function so only a single integral wavelet function is calculated but since Bi-orthogonal is not orthogonal so there are two integral wavelet functions are calculated, one for decomposition and another one for reconstruction. **Figure 3.2**

shows the decomposition of a sample normal brain image and a sample brain image with Alzheimer disease (both in axial plane) using integrated Haar wavelet. Similarly, **Figure 3.3** shows the same using integrated Bi-orthogonal 1.3 wavelet function. The images are decomposed by above techniques up to level 3. Each level consists of *approximation coefficient, horizontal details, vertical details and diagonal details*.

Algorithm or pseudo code for dataset construction

Algorithm 3.1 Dataset Construction

Input : Let I is the total number of brain images collected each having size 256×256

Output: Feature matrix constructed from images

Step 1: Take IMG_k , the image taken for decomposition using IDWT for $k=1$ to I

Step 2: Initialize $C_k = 32 \times 32$ to store feature vector for each image

Step 3: Find Integration of *Haar* wavelet function $Wavelet_1 =$

$intergrate_Wavelet('Haar')$

Step 4: Find Integration of *Bi-orthogonal 1.3* wavelet function $Wavelet_2 =$

$intergrate_Wavelet('Bior1.3')$

Step 5: Find 1st, 2nd and 3rd level of coefficients using IDWT,

$$ll3_h, (lh3_h, hl3_h, hh3_h) = pywt.wavelet (Wavelet_1)$$

$$ll3_b, (lh3_b, hl3_b, hh3_b) = pywt.wavelet (Wavelet_2)$$

Step 6: for $i = 1$ to 32

Step 7: for $j = 1$ to 32

Step 8: $C_K = ll3_h + ll3_b$

Step 9: $IMG_k = C_k$

3.1 Result Analysis and Discussion

To validate the above proposed model various experimental evaluations have been carried out. All the experiments have been performed using Python 2.7 platform with few basic packages like numpy, scipy, matplotlib and scikitlearn on a personal computer with 3.40 GHz Core-i7 processor and 4 GB RAM, running under Ubuntu operating system. The performance of the classifier models have been evaluated by using different matrices such as *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall* and *F1-score*. All the classifier models have been validated by using a *k*-fold cross validation where *k* value is considered as 5.

Table 3.1 Performance comparisons of different classifiers for classification of brain diseases using features extracted from brain images

Classification Techniques	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	F1-Score
MLPNN	0.85 ±0.32	0.85±0.32	0.90±0.30	0.87±0.31
Gaussian NB	0.80±0.24	0.80±0.24	1.00±0.00	0.87±0.16
Logistic Regression	0.95±0.15	0.90±0.30	0.90±0.30	0.90±0.30
SVM with Linear Kernel	0.95±0.15	0.90±0.30	0.90±0.30	0.90±0.30
SVM with Polynomial Kernel	1.00 ±0.00	1.00 ±0.00	1.00 ±0.00	1.00 ±0.00

Table 3.2 Parameter setup for classifier

Classification Techniques	Parameters
MLPNN	Activation Function – Sigmoid, Learning Rate = 0.7 Momentum Coefficient = 0.8, Input Bias – Yes
Gaussian NB	Prior probabilities – Random, Theta – mean of each feature per class, Sigma – Variance of each feature per class
Logistic Regression	Inverse of regularization strength (C) – 1.0, Intercept scaling -1, Maximum iteration – 100, Tolerance – 1e-4
SVM with Linear Kernel	Kernel Type – Linear, Penalty Factor = 1.0
SVM with Polynomial Kernel	Kernel Type – Polynomial, Degree – 3, Penalty Factor = 1.0

Table 3.3 Performance comparison of proposed method with other existing techniques

Author	Techniques	Accuracy
Sandeep Chaplot <i>et al.</i> (2006) [143]	DWT, SVM (Polynomial)	0.9715
	DWT, SVM (RBF)	0.9733
S. Das <i>et al.</i> (2013) [132]	RT, PCA, LS-SVM	1.0000
M. Saritha <i>et al.</i> (2013) [131]	DWT, WE, SWP, PNN	0.9988
Y. Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2010) [133]	DWT, PCA, FNN, ACPSO	0.9875
El-Dahshan <i>et al.</i> (2014) [134]	FPCNN, DWT, PCA, FPANN	0.9888
	SWT, PCA, IABAP-FNN	0.9944
S. Wang <i>et al.</i> (2015) [135]	SWT, PCA, ABC-SPSO-FNN	0..9975

	DWT, PCA, FPANN	0.9698
El-Dahshan <i>et al.</i> (2010) [130]	DWT, PCA, <i>k</i> -NN	0.9754
Proposed Method (IDWT)	IDWT, SVM (Polynomial)	1.0000

The following are the observations of the experimentation and validation.

- (a) Different sets of training testing samples are considered for each validation set. After the testing of all validation sets the mean and standard deviation of the *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall* and *F1-score* has been represented in the **Table 3.1**.
- (b) From this **Table 3.1**, it can be clearly understood that the performance of *SVM with Polynomial Kernel* is best as compared all other techniques. Accuracy of SVM with linear kernel and logistic regression is same but better as compared to Gaussian NB and MLPNN.
- (c) In this chapter, we have considered SVM as the primary classification algorithm for classification of brain diseases. SVM is the most popularly used machine learning based classification for multi-dimensional feature space classification. It generally transforms the data set into a high dimensional space where it separates different classes by the help of a hyper plane. The kernel functions play an important role in support vector classification. The most popularly used kernel functions are *linear*, *polynomial* and *RBF* kernel function. Here, we have represented two kernel functions such as; *linear* and *polynomial*.
- (d) The SVM classifier is provided with the dataset constructed from brain images by using above mentioned techniques. To compare the performance of SVM classifier with other classifiers such as; MLPNN, Naïve Bayesian network and Logistic Regression are considered for evaluation of the proposed IDWT model and the parameters considered for MLPNN, Gaussian NB, Logistic Regression, SVM with linear kernel and polynomial kernels are detailed in **Table 3.2**.
- (e) Finally, the proposed IDWT has been compared with few existing and state-of-the-art

strategies being proposed by various researchers as discussed in literature survey and from this comparison also it can be observed from **Table 3.3**, proposed IDWT with SVM Polynomial Kernel is outperforming all the methods with 100% accuracy.

- (f) Where x is the real signal, ψ is an arbitrary mother wavelet, a is the scale and b is the translation (X is the processed signal of course). The scale is the same as the size of the window. Here the illustrations using Morlet Wavelet.
- (g) The goal of the SVM algorithm is to create the best line or decision boundary that can segregate n -dimensional space into classes so that we can easily put the new data point in the correct category in the future. SVM algorithm can be used for Face detection, image classification, text categorization, etc.

CHAPTER-4

Medical images such as; MRI, CT, PET etc. plays an important role in aiding to diagnose, treatment and to keep the record of those images which can be used in future. In recent years, advances in digital imaging technologies are generating huge volume of digital images and also now a days, hospitals and clinics are having large collection of numerous online medical images for the study purpose. In hospitals, patient's health records in the form of digital images need manipulation, organization, processing and handling of data by the computers and this makes the requirement of computer assisted systems in the form of decision support systems which can guide to diagnose the diseases. Considering the above-mentioned facts, the image processing is one the emerging and fastest growing technology in the computer science field, where the scientists are working to develop numerous computational models [74] [77]. The quantitative analysis of medical images such as; MRI, CT, PET etc. can be enhanced using image processing, analysing and visualizing those images. The main objectives of image processing area are; (a) to develop computational models and algorithms; (b) to collaborate and help the research community for information analysis and proper visualization of biomedical research problems; and (c) to develop various computational tools which and be used to support the discovery and advancement of biomedical images [74-77].

Medical image analysis process consists of basically three phases, such as; feature extraction and representation of extracted features in readable format for any algorithm, feature selection, which will extract the relevant or significant features which can be properly used by any classifier and finally, feature and image classification. In current scenario, there are not enough radiologists to handle the growing volumes of data being captured by X-rays, MRIs, PET, CT and ultrasounds. Therefore, this era is in need of automated image analysis models to ease their burden by eliminating the need of scrutinization, searching for anomalies etc. and also physicians and clinician can more focus on their clinical aspects of diagnosing through those CAD based models [76-78].

The process of assigning pixels in the image to any category or classes and in order to classify is called as image processing and in this relationship between the data or images and classes must be considered properly which is known as training process and key this accurate classification is, proper training of the classifiers or algorithms. Two important steps of accurate classification is application of proper learning techniques and selection of feature sets, though with the learning process will take over. Supervised and unsupervised are two kinds of learning processes. In supervised learning, a teacher or model is involved in the learning process, but there is no teacher or model is available in the unsupervised learning mechanism, it explores the data space to discover the underlying properties of the data distribution to identify the class or category of a record or image.

The recent research establishes that, ANN are the most promising approaches for image classification and are best alternatives to different conventional classification methodologies or algorithms. The non-linearity of ANN model, ease of using ANN to treat the complicated problems with a simple approach, it's parallel architectures with multi-core processor or GPUs makes the ANN faster, the self-adaptive methods and it can adjust itself without explicit specification of underlying distribution of data and functions, and identifies the features accurately, estimating the posterior probabilities to establish the classification rules and to perform statistical analysis and, it is adaptive property to complex problems makes the use ANN wide enough[74-78]. Though, traditional ANNs have above mentioned advantages, it also suffers from few disadvantages, such as; in the ANN's the relationship between input and output cannot be interpreted when the complexities of the system increases, other methods are combined and used for modelling. Recently, *deep learning* which is a advanced from of ANN is doing justice to all the valuable data in almost all the fields of speech recognition, image processing, natural language processing, financial engineering and health care research. Deep learning is used to obtain and learn the useful features with multiple level of abstraction [79]. The deep learning strategy uses the multiple layers of non-linear processing unit, where each successive layer takes output of previous layer as an input to the current layer. A hierarchical data representation of data is formed due to the multiple level of data processing and this high level of learning with low supervision. The various deep learning-based approaches include Recurrent Neural networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory/ Gated RecurrentUnit (LSTM/GRU), Deep Belief Networks

(DBNs), CNNs and Deep Stacking Networks (DSNs) [77-80]. DBN is a class of ANN comprising of multiple layers of graphical models with directed and undirected edges. Its architecture composed of multiple hidden layers and each layer being connected with each other. Each layer in the DBN is RBM stacked against each other and the algorithm of DBN evolves in three major steps such as; (a) Contrastive Divergence (CD) algorithm is used to train the DBN to learn the feature from the visible units, (b) the previously trained features as visible units are used as input to the second hidden layer and so on, i.e. the training is done sequentially from bottom layer to top layer and finally; (c) the complete DBN network is trained, when the learning of final hidden layer is complete, each layer learn a higher level representation of the layer below [3-7]. This strategy is kind of unsupervised approach, where the training criterion does not depend on the class labels. The efficient use of hidden layers, robustness in classification problem, the unsupervised approach of training and the use of outputs of each layer making the output stochastic, the unsupervised learning approach based on energy rather than minimizing the reconstruction error makes the DBN superior to ANN for data classification. Deep learning approaches can extract the features from the data automatically to solve the problem of feature extraction through its hierarchical structure. No one can guarantee the correctness of the extracted features because; there is no corresponding theoretical and mathematical meaning available for those extracted features [78-80].

Therefore, to solve this cited issue, an improved DBN based image classification model has been proposed and experimented by combining the DWT and PCA for feature extraction and to get a reduced size of those extracted features. As we know, the architecture of DBN is composed of stacked RBMs to obtain the relevant and significant features. In general, the architecture of DBN uses multiple hidden layers with huge number of hidden units to learn best features from the raw pixels of image data, thereby increasing the training time. In this work, therefore, an attempt has been made to integrate the architecture of DBN with wavelet transform to reduce the complexities associated with training time. The extracted low-resolution images from DWT are used for training DBN in this proposed image classification model and this proposed model has been named as DWT-PCA-DBN image classifier. The proposed model has been experimented with deep learning based approaches such as traditional DBN, PCA-DBN with non-deep learning based approaches of variants of ANN such as; MLPNN [157-158], RNN[159],

RBFNN [160], ELM [12-16], Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) [161-166] and Time Delay Neural Network (TDNN) [163-165]. Additionally, the performance of the proposed classifier has been evaluated based on number of epochs for training of RBN and weight Initialization and finally the statistical validation has been performed based on *McNemar's test* [166-168].

Pilot Study for Proposed DWT-PCA-DBN Image Classification

We have conducted pilot study on image datasets we have collected 15 training samples were collected and 5 testing samples have been collected on Alzheimer diseases datasets and remaining datasets has been collected from open-source platform, where different image datasets from different patients have been publicly provided for only research purpose.

Based on this study we have different image datasets available on open source and we have collected some image data sets from pilot study we have made reliability and consistency has been made on the datasets and we also calculated accurate result analysis has done on this study

Total number of datasets available and total number of pilot datasets available for different image diseases has been consider.

Form datasets collection we have gathered data from government reputed institutes we have gather the data we presented the data for the website https://open.alberta.ca/dataset/gda-dig_2015_0062/resource/82c63fa8-06d0-4fc1-96ef-f7b76616f34e for open-source datasets data have been collected form <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/public/rider+Neuro+MRI>

Total number of open-source data and pilot data

Source	Total number of datasets available	Total number datasets collected	Total number of training samples	Total number of testing samples
Open-source platform	70220	10000	200	56
Pilot data Samples	15000	100	15	5

we conducted different experiments on these bases, and we obtain accurate results we have got from analysis on different set of datasets whereas in pilot analysis we have performed accuracy on the testingsample we have achieved 99.49. when contrasted with study on the on the open-source datasets we have been contrasted investigation and computational and the informational indexes The pilot investigation of the flow research was the initial step of the functional use of the Gestalt play treatmententhusiastic insight customized for elementary younger students. It is additionally the last advance of the main gathering of steps of a mediation research study (De Vos, 2002:409-418) in particular, "Early turn of events and pilot testing". This section covers a hypothetical foundation of the definition and worth of pilot considers. It likewise covers the objective of the pilot study – what the scientist anticipates from a pilot study. The analyst then, at that point, examines the utilization of the pilot study in the ebb and flow research. The results of the pilot study will likewise be examined presently, on the grounds that these impact the real exploration itself. The specialist will initially characterize a pilot study and express the worth thereof following the prologue to explain what a pilot concentrate truly is and why it is required in the examination interaction.

A pilot study is a smaller than expected form of a full-scale study or a preliminary attempt done in arrangement of the total review. The last is likewise called a 'attainability' study. It can likewise be a particular pre-testing of examination instruments, including polls or meeting plans. (Analyze Polit, et al. and Baker in Nursing Standard, 2002:33-44; Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001:1.) The pilot study will in this manner trail the scientist has an unmistakable vision of the exploration theme and questions, the procedures and strategies, which will be applied, and what the examination timetable will resemble. It is "reassessment without tears" (Blaxter, Hughes and 257 Tight, 1996:121), evaluating all examination strategies and techniques, which the specialist has at the top of the priority list to perceive how well they will function practically speaking. On the off chance that essential it can, in any case be adjusted and changed in like manner. (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 1996:121) The pilot study in the flow examination can be characterized as for the most part a give a shot of exploration strategies and techniques, yet in addition of polls and meetings. The analyst accumulated a passionate insight program and applied this to a pilot gathering of elementary younger students. During this interaction, the scientist likewise tried a short open-ended

poll on the way of life of the groups of the kids, surveys on their learning styles for the guardians, a conduct style instrument/poll on the kids in the pilot gathering and input investigates these to the guardians. The pilot investigation of the flow examination can thusly be characterized as both a plausibility concentrates just as a pre-testing of instruments, polls and meetings.

The analyst previously examined the worth of a pilot study as expressed by various creators and afterward the relevance to the current review in the accompanying passages. Subsequent to expressing the worth of such a review, the analyst arranged the objective of a pilot study for the ebb and flow research project. The scientist sees the objective of a pilot concentrate overall as identified with the point of the examination undertaking of which it frames part. The overall objective of a pilot study is to give data, which can add to the accomplishment of the examination project all in all. The last is upheld by the accompanying statements concerning the worth and objective of pilot contemplates: "to check whether the monster will fly" (De Vos, 2002:410), "reassessment without tears" (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 1996:121), and "Don't face the challenge. Pilot test first." (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001:2). The overall objective accordingly appears to save some time, exertion and cash, which can be lost if a significant examination study falls flat in view of unexpected qualities. The objective is hence to test the review on limited scope first to figure out every one of the potential issues that may prompt disappointment of the examination methodology. It may limit the danger of disappointment.

Schematic Layout of Proposed DWT-PCA-DBN Image Classifier

In this research work, we have proposed a novel brain MRI image classification technique using a combination of DWT with PCA and deep DBN. Before performing classification task, the wavelet transform has been applied to extract the features. The datasets have been collected from [169] and are being supported and maintained by University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences (UAMS) which are in Grey Scale DICOM format of 256×256 size.

Feature extraction from brain images plays a vital role to eliminate or reduce the dimension as well as to extract useful features which are relevant for improving the accuracy of the classifiers. Many feature extraction strategies have been proposed, but it has been observed that, most of them only exploit the information from the data space while neglecting the useful contained in the feature space. The proposed strategy for image classification exploits the feature extraction and image classification in three phases; in the data pre-processing phase, the features are extracted using DWT, in the dimensionality reduction phase, reduced number of features are obtained using PCA and finally, three layers of RBN stacked method has been proposed for image classification using DBN as shown in **Figure 4.1**.

Figure 5.1 A Three-layer RBM stacking based approach for image classification (DWT-PCA-DBN)

4.1 Reference: DBN [78-80].-Methodologies Adopted for Experimentation

Deep Belief Network (DBN)

Generally, DBNs are generative neural networks that stack RBMs. RBMs can also be thought of as being generative auto encoders with many layers of hidden explanatory factors which uses a greedy layer-wise unsupervised learning algorithm. RBMs are the basic building blocks and used

for training the deeper models. DBNs for image classification are best suitable if all images are aligned by means of size, translation and rotation. Belief networks and RBMs are the basic ingredients of DBN [78-80]. The belief network is having weighted connections with stochastic binary units. In this study, our basic objective is to find the states of binary units and adjustment of weights, where the states of the binary units in belief network is having a value 0 or 1, probability is 1 which is determined by a bias and weighted input from other units. The probability equation used is given in (5.1).

$$P(s_j = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-s_j w_{ji})}$$

A stochastic recurrent neural network with stochastic binary units and undirected edges between the units makes the structure of the Boltzman machine. But RBM has one layer of hidden units and restricts connection between hidden units which allows more efficient learning algorithm. Mainly there are two layers those are visible layer and hidden layer. The energy function for probability distribution over hidden and visible units is defined in (4.2).

$$P(v, h) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(-E(v, h)) \tag{4.2}$$

Where, $Z = \sum_{v,h} \exp(-E(v, h))$ (4.3)

The unsupervised training phase of DBN is followed by a fine-tuning process and the steps can be detailed as follows:

- (a) First, RBM layer is trained using original/scaled data as inputs to its visible layers and is iterated for sufficiently large number of epochs.
- (b) The representative data obtained from the RBM's first layer is given as input to the RBM's second layer's visible units.
- (c) Each subsequent layers of RBM are trained as mentioned in (b) to obtain good initialization parameters for the stable network.

- (d) Finally, the fine tuning of the parameters of the DBN network is done using a supervised classifier.

Discrete Wavelet Transform

DWT is a very powerful tool for feature extraction from images as well as non-stationary signals. DWT is generally considered as the most efficient technique for image decomposition and feature extraction. This is mainly popular because it analyses signal or image at different scales of resolution. Therefore, it is useful for detailed analysis of images. In this work, the *bi-orthogonal wavelet function* in which the wavelet function is not necessarily orthogonal, but it is invertible (5.1). has been experimented. In this case two scaling functions ($\phi(x)$) are used which are associated with two different wavelet functions

wavelet it may generate different multi-resolution analyses. The images are decomposed by above techniques up to level 3. In each level, four sub-band images are formed. Each level consists of *approximation coefficient, horizontal details, vertical details* and *diagonal details* [33-34].

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA is a competent method to reduce the high dimensional dataset, having the interrelated attributes keeping a large number of variations. It can be successfully achieved through transforming the dataset in to a new dataset according to their variances. PCA is having three stages: The components of the input vector is orthogonalized, the resulting orthogonal components is arranged in such a way that the largest variation should come first, the components having very least contributions towards the variation should be eliminated in the dataset. PCA project the data in to a sub space to minimize the reconstruction error in the sense of mean squared.

In this chapter, for experimentation and comparison of proposed image classifier, the following classifiers are used throughout the study.

Classifiers used for experimentation.

MLPNN usually consist of three types of layers such as an input layer, number of hidden layers and an output layer, for which sometimes it is called as layered networks. For MLP the most common algorithm is error back propagation, and this can be used as one of the optimized approach to meet the desired output. MLP is having its own [170-171] limitations; the potential of error back propagation learning algorithm to converge in local minima may create an impractical towards the field of real applications. RNN [172] is found to be a highly promising tool for image classification. In RNN, the weight of the network is updated using a dynamic learning algorithm, to exhibit the necessary properties. Gradient descent algorithm is used to adjust the weight value opposite to the direction of gradient. It is well known basically for the feedback path from output node to the input node, where the current output depends upon the result of the past output. Simultaneously the error not only depends on the current parameter but also it depends up on the past parameter.

RBFNN directly operates in the input. RBFNN training is having two phases: supervised as well as unsupervised phases. In an unsupervised phase the receptive field number is defined and then the center as well as the spread of receptive field is decided using the clustering algorithm. Using the pseudo inverse weights connected between the output of RBFNN and receptive fields are calculated. The index of performance is figured out through mean square error. To find out a successful RBFNN model, an appropriate number of receptive fields should be selected [171-173]. ELM is a single layer feed [173] forward neural network, where the hidden layers need not to be tuned at each iteration. It analytically determines the output weights by using simple generalized inverse operations of the output matrices of the hidden layer. As ELM is free from iterations, hence the computational time needed for training in ELM is faster than traditional feed forward neural network. Comparative to other traditional algorithm ELM is having smallest training error as well as smallest norms of weight and also runs extremely faster than the most popular SLFN with the best generalization performance, in this context it seems to [174] be

named as extreme learning machine.

PNN [164] is an efficient tool for the classification of image; it works efficiently basically for high dimensional data. The weights as well as the functions of the network backed by using straight forward Bayesian probability and the other network models, which is to be optimized using gradient descent will be edged through the above network. In TDNN [163-165], the hidden layer is connected to the output layer in a feed forward way but the basic concept behind TDNN is about the connection of hidden units. The hidden units are connected to a limited number of input units representing a consecutive number of patterns. Those hidden units are having the receptive fields sensitive to a portion of input window. There is a restriction that at each position in the input, the same receptive field has to be present at once only. The hidden units are denominated as feature unit as it will make out certain features in the input window regardless of its positions. At the time of learning derivatives of the corresponding weights are calculated since activation functions are different for the hidden units with their receptive fields at positions, which is different for the input window.

Experimentation and Model Evaluation

Experimental setup

To validate the above proposed model various experimental evaluations have been carried out. All the experiments have been performed using Python 2.7 platform with few basic packages like numpy, scilpy, matplotlib and some data analysis packages like TensorFlow, keras and scikit-learn on a personal computer with 3.40 GHz Core-i7 processor and 4 GB RAM, running under Ubuntu operating system. To validate our experimental design, we compare the proposed hybridized image classifier with standard heterogeneous classifiers such as MLPNN, RNN, RBFN, ELM, PNN, TDNN etc. The validation procedure of proposed classifier works in various stages as discusses in Section 6 for four datasets used for this experimentation.

Datasets description

For this research work we have used RIDER (Reference Image Database to Evaluate Therapy Response) Neuro MRI which contains imaging data on 19 patients with recurrent glioblastoma who underwent repeat imaging sets. These images were obtained approximately 2 days apart (with the exception of one patient, RIDER Neuro MRI-1086100996, whose images were obtained one day apart). All 19 patients had repeat dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI) datasets on the same 1.5T imaging magnet. On the basis of T2-weighted images, technologists chose 16 image locations using 5mm thick contiguous slices for the imaging. For T1 mapping, multi-flip 3D FLASH images were obtained using flip angles of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 degrees, TR of 4.43 ms, TE of 2.1 ms, 2 signal averages.

Dynamic images were obtained during the intravenous injection of 0.1mmol/kg of Magnevist intravenous at 3ccs/second; started 24 seconds after the scan had begun. The dynamic images were acquired using a 3D FLASH technique, using a flip angle of 25 degrees, TR of 3.8 ms, TE of 1.8 ms using a $1 \times 1 \times 5$ mm voxel size. The 16 slice imaging set was obtained every 4.8 sec. Seventeen of the 19 patients also obtained repeat diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) sets. Whole brain DTI were obtained using TR 6000ms, TE 100 ms, 90 degree flip angle, 4 signal averages, matrix 128×128 , $1.72 \times 1.72 \times 5$ mm voxel size, 12 tensor directions, iPAT 2, b value of 1000 sec/mm². All 19 patients underwent whole brain 3D FLASH imaging in the sagittal plane after the administration of Magnevist. For this sequence, TR was 8.6 ms, TE 4.1 ms, 20 degree flip angle, 1 signal average, matrix 256×256 ; 1mm isotropic voxel size. All 17 patients who had repeat DTI sets also had 3D FLAIR sequences in the sagittal plane after the administration of Magnevist. For this sequence, the TR was 6000 ms, TE 353 ms, and TI 2200ms; 180 degree flip angle, 1 signal average, matrix 256×216 ; 1 mm isotropic voxel size. Before transmission to NCIA, all image sets with 1mm isotropic voxel size were defaced using MIPAV software or manually. All the images collected are in DICOM format and they have been processed using python program and the total size of the image dataset is 7.3GB.

Parameters setup

The parameters need to be specified carefully for DBN, as it is the backbone of the above proposed model. As a deep learning architecture DBN consists of a stack of RBMs that accomplish the task of DBN collectively. The values set for the various parameters selected for three RBMs such as; RBM1, RBM2 and RBM3 are detailed in **Table 4.1**.

Table 5.1 Parameter setup

Parameters	I N e		
	RBM1	RBM2	RBM3
Visible Units	40000	1000	500
Latent Units	Binary	Binary	Binary
No. of Latent Units	1000	500	300
Performance	Free energy	Free energy	Free energy
Max Epoch	100	100	100
Learning Rate	0.1	0.1	0.1
Model	Generative	Generative	Generative

4.4.3 Algorithms proposed.

This section describes the steps involved in RBM procedure for Sigmoidal units in **Algorithm 4.1** and process of DBN learning in **Algorithm 5.2**.

Algorithm 4.1 RBM procedure for Sigmoidal units

x is sample from the training distribution of RBM, ε is a learning rate w is the RBM weight matrix, of dimension (number of hidden units, number of inputs), b is the RBM biases vector for hidden units, c is the RBM biases vector for input units.

Step 1: RBM(x, ε, w, b, c); Step2:

For all hidden units i ;

Compute $Q(h[0][i] = 1/(1 + \exp(x[0])))$

for Gaussian units, Sigmoid [$b[i] + \sum_j(w[i][j] \times x[0][j])$])

Sample $h[0][i]$ from $Q(h[0][i] = 1/(1 + \exp(x[0])))$

End for

Step 3: **For** all visible units j :

Compute $P(v[1][j] = 1/(1 + \exp(h[0])))$

for Gaussian units (Sigmoid [$c[j] + \sum_i(w[i][j] \times h[0][i])$])

Sample $v[1][j]$ from $P(v[1][j] = 1/(1 + \exp(h[0])))$

End for

Step 4: **For** all hidden units i :

Compute $Q(h[1][i] = 1/(1 + \exp(x[01])))$

for binomial units, Sigmoid [$b[i] + \sum_j(w[i][j] \times x[1][j])$])

End for

$W += c \times (h[0] \times x[0]^T - Q(h[1][.] = 1|v[1]) \times x[1]^T$

$b += c \times (h[0] - Q(h[1][.] = 1|x[1]))$

$C += c \times (x[0] - x[1])$

Algorithm 4.2 DBN learning procedure

Z is the supervised training distribution for the DBN, with *(input, target)* samples (x, y) , C is a training criterion, a function that takes a network output $f(x)$ and a target y and returns a scalar differentiable in $f(x)$, ϵ_C is a learning rate for the stochastic gradient descent on supervised cost C , L is the number of layers, $n=(n[1], \dots, n[L])$ is the number of hidden units in each layer, $W[i]$ is the weight matrix for level i , for i from 1 to L , $b[i]$ is the bias vector for level i , for i from 1 to L , V is a weight matrix for the supervised output layer of the network and c is the bias vector for the supervised output layer.

Step 1: DBN ($Z, C, \epsilon_C, L, n, W, b, V, c$);

Step 2: Recursively define mean-field propagation

$$\mu[i](x) = \text{Expectation}(g[i]|g[i-1] = \mu[i-1](x))$$

Where, $\mu[0](x) = x$ and $\text{Expectation}(g[i]|g[i-1] = \mu[i-1])$ is the expected value of $g[i]$ under the RBN conditional distribution $Q(g[i]|g[i-1])$,

Step 3: When the values of $g[i-1]$ are replaced by the mean-field values $\mu[i-1](x)$

In the case where, $g[i]$ has Gaussian units:

$$\# \text{Expectation}(g[i][j]|g[i-1] = \mu[i-1]) =$$

$$\text{sigmoid}(b[i][j] + \sum_k W[i][j][k] \mu[i-1][k](x))$$

Step 4: Define the network output function $f(x) = V \times \mu[L](x)' + c$

Step 5: Iteratively minimize the expected value of $C(f(x), y)$.

Step 6: For pairs (x, y) sampled from Z by tuning parameters W, b, V, c .

This can be done by stochastic gradient descent with learning rate ϵ_C , using an appropriate stopping criterion such as early stopping on a validation set.

Experimentation and Model Evaluation

Different experiments have been performed to evaluate the performance of DWT-PCA-DBN based classifiers. All the experiments have been carried out using Python programming environment. Since, the dataset size very huge, it is practically not possible to carry out all the experiments in a normal laptop or pc. Hence, we have used a local cloud server with high end configurations and also with GPU support. To compare the performances among several settings, we have trained DBN with various parameters and structures and computed the results of training and testing errors for each scenario. To compare the performance with other classification techniques, various performance measurement metrics such as classification accuracy, specificity, sensitivity and F-score are being measured. The total experimentation process can be compiled in various stages as detailed below.

- (a) *Deep vs. Non deep learning methods:* For the comparison purpose, in the first fold, the performance comparison between deep learning based proposed DWT-PCA-DBN approach and non-deep learning-based methods such as; MLPNN, RNN, RBFN, ELM, PNN, TDNN have been done as shown in **Table 4.2** based on classification accuracy, specificity, sensitivity and F-score. From this **Table 4.2**, it can be very well understood that, proposed deep learning based proposed DWT-PCA-DBN image classification model is showing significant improved result over non deep learning-based methods. Then, in second fold of validation gain the performance comparison has been established among traditional DBN, DWT-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN as detailed in **Table 4.3**. From both the tables, it can be concluded that, the performance of DWT-PCA-DBN is more as compared to other techniques as deep learning approach is more efficient for image classification task and also the DWT-PCA-DBN

technique outperforms the general DBN as there are more streamlining of feature selection has been done through DWT-PCA approach.

Table 4.2 Deep learning vs. non deep learning based approaches

Classification Techniques	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	F-Score
MLP	0.85±0.33	0.83±0.26	0.87±0.22	0.84±0.30
RNN	0.87±0.23	0.88±0.31	0.85±0.21	0.84±0.29
RBFNN	0.79±0.22	0.75±0.23	0.74±0.34	0.74±0.21
ELM	0.90±0.15	0.87±0.32	0.91±0.22	0.89±0.25
PNN	0.89±0.18	0.90±0.28	0.87±0.29	0.88±0.32
TDNN	0.86±0.32	0.85±0.25	0.88±0.23	0.86±0.29
DWT-PCA-DBN	0.95±0.14	0.94±0.16	0.97±0.26	0.95±0.15

Table 4.3 Performance comparison between DBN, DWT-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN

Classification Techniques	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	F-Score
DBN	0.89±0.18	0.88±0.26	0.91±0.19	0.90±0.22
DWT-DBN	0.91±0.19	0.90±0.24	0.92±0.18	0.91±0.23
DWT-PCA-DBN	0.95±0.14	0.94±0.16	0.97±0.26	0.95±0.15

- (b) *Number of epochs for training of RBN:* In this work, the DBN consists of three layers of RBN such as RBN1, RBN2 and RBN3 and training of those RBN algorithms require certain number of iterations or epochs to converge into an optimal value. A failure to obtain an optimal value for each RBM results in poor performance of overall system since RBM is a basic building block of the proposed DWT-PCA-DBN image classifier. It seems that, executing several iterations yields better results, but in fact, it takes long time

to train and also over-fitting the data occurs, therefore, it is advisable to stop before the over-fitting occurs. The error graphs shows the performance in the form of convergence with respect to number of epochs in **Figure 4.2**, **Figure 4.3** and **Figure 4.4** for three different layers (RMB 1: layer 1, RBM 2: layer 2 and RBM 3:layer 3) for DBM, PCA-DBM and DWT-PCA-DBM respectively. From **Figure 4.2**, it can be clearly seen that, layer 3 gradually decreases from 40 till 100 numbers of epochs showing much better performance and layer 1 and layer 2 shows zig-zag movement from 30 to 100 number of epochs which is a sign of over fitting for traditional DBN network. From this,it concludes that, 40 epochs is the best setting for DBN image classifier.

Figure 4.2. Error graph for different numberof layers for DBN

Figure 4.3. Error graph for different number of layers for PCA-DBN

Similarly, **Figure 4.3** and **Figure 4.4**, it can be seen that, layer 3 converges at 50 epochs and 70 epochs for PCA-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN image classifiers respectively. While comparing the convergence of all three networks with respect to number of epochs and errors occurred, it can be concluded that proposed DWT-PCA-DBM is showing best setting with optimal value of error and epochs.

- (c) *Weight Initialization:* Weights initialization is one of the most effective approaches in speeding up the training of a neural network. In fact, it influences not only the speed of convergence, but also the probability of convergence and the generalization. Using too small or too large values could speed the learning, but at the same time, it may end up performing worse.

Figure 4.5. Error graph for different weight initialization methods for DBN

Figure 4.6. Error graph for different number of layers for PCA-DBN

Figure 4.7. Error graph for different numberof layers for proposed DWT-PCA-DBN

Figure 4.8. Error graph for different techniques such as; DBN, PCA-DBN and proposed DWT-PCA-DBN

In addition, the number of iterations of the training algorithm and the convergence time would vary depending on the initialized values. In this phase of performance validation, considering weight initialization for all three individual deep learning-based networks and also among three are methods have been measured and given in **Figure 4.5**, **Figure 4.6**, **Figure 4.7**and **Figure 4.8**.

Three different initialization methods have been applied during the training of 100 epochs such as; (a) small weights between 0 and 1; (b) large weights between 1 and 10 and;

(c) initializing with zero weights. For DBN network from **Figure 4.5**, it can be seen that, initializing the weights of DBN network with all the types of random values results in converging from 40 epochs but experimenting with small random weights results in least error. PCA-DBN network as shown in **Figure 4.6** also shows better convergence and less error with

network shown in **Figure 4.7**, experimenting with small values for weight initialization helps the network with least error, though, it converges at 70 epochs. While comparing among all three networks from **Figure 4.8**, it can be concluded that, proposed DWT-PCA-DBN network for image classification is showing outstanding performance with respect to the number epochs and error. DBN network is converging at 40 epochs, while PCA-DBN is at 100 epochs and DWT-PCA-DBN is 70 epochs with least error in comparison to other two networks.

(d) *Statistical Analysis*: Two level statistical analysis such as McMemar’s test and overall accuracies, average accuracies, and Kappa statistics for training sets and testing sets have been conducted for DBN, DWT-PCA and DWT-PCA-DBN as detailed below.

o The McNemar’s test, which is based upon the standardized normal test statistic, is used to demonstrate whether the two methods perform differently in the statistical sense. The statistic is computed using (4.4).

$$MN_{ij} = \frac{mn_{ij} - mn_{ji}}{\sqrt{mn_{ij} + mn_{ji}}} \quad (4.4)$$

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(b-c)^2}{(b+c)} \quad (4.5)$$

(mn_{ij} + mn_{ji})

$$mn_{ij} = mn_{ji} = \frac{1}{2}$$

Where, mn_{ij} denotes number of samples misclassified by I classifier but not by j classifier.

Similarly mn_{ji} denotes number of samples misclassified by j classifier but not by I classifier.

This is basically derived from the chi-squared distribution using (5.5).

Under the null hypothesis mn_{ij} is equal to mn_{ji} . That is equivalent to the number of counts for (5.6).

At 95% level of confidence, the difference of accuracies between the two methods

(DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN) is significant as $|mn_{ij}| = 3.841$ which is greater than 1.96.

Hence the null hypothesis can be rejected. Similarly at 95% level of confidence the

difference of accuracies between the two methods (DWT-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN) is

significant as $|mn_{ji}| = 2.147$ which is greater than 1.96.

Hence, the null hypothesis can be rejected and the alternative hypothesis can be accepted

that states there is a significant difference between the corresponding two different classifiers.

o Measuring the overall accuracies (OAs), average accuracies (AAs), and Kappa statistics (Kappa) of ten runs of trainings and tests of DWT, PCA-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN.

Table 4.4 Performance comparison based on OAs, AAs and Kappa statistics for DBN, DWT-DBN and proposed DWT-PCA-DBN

Classifiers	OAs	AAs	Kappa
DBN	91%	89%	0.4811
DWT-DBN	93%	91%	0.5732
DWT-PCA-DBN	97%	95%	0.6522

Result Analysis and Discussion

The use and development of computational models for medical image diagnosis raised a new level of interventional treatment and medical image processing is now one of the most popular ways to effectively and quickly diagnose the diseases and also it enables the doctors to quickly interpret the medical images accurately. As a solution, machine learning techniques are now-a-days being used to automate the diagnosis process. However, traditional machine learning methods are not sufficient to deal with complex problems. Therefore, deep learning methods are trying to resolve the limitations of machine learning based techniques. In this work, an attempt has been made to show a clear cut differentiation between deep learning based methods and non-deep learning based methods for image classification. The following are few observations of the current study that makes it challenging and interesting for image classification.

- (a) For this research work we have used RIDER Neuro MRI data which contains imaging data on 19 patients with recurrent glioblastoma who underwent repeat imaging sets.
- (b) Though, the dataset size very huge, a local cloud server with high end configurations and also with GPU support and Python has been used for experimentation.
- (c) To compare the performances among several settings, the DBN has been trained with various parameters and structures and computed the results of training and testing errors foreach scenario.
- (d) To compare the performance with other classification techniques, various performance measurement metrics such as classification accuracy, specificity, sensitivity and F-score arebeing measured.
- (e) For a clear cut comparison has been obtained between deep learning and non-deep learningbased strategies and from **Table 4.2**, it can be very well realized that, proposed deep learning based proposed DWT-PCA-DBN image classification model is showing significant improved result over non deep learning based methods.

- (f) The performance comparison has also been established among traditional DBN, DWT- DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN and it can be concluded from **Table 4.3** that, the performance of DWT-PCA-DBN is more as compared to other techniques as deep learning approach is more efficient for image classification task and also the DWT-PCA-DBN technique outperforms the general DBN as there are more streamlining of feature selection has been done through DWT-PCA approach.
- (g) Considering the number of epochs required for training the RBN network, from **Figure 4.2** it can be observed that, layer 3 gradually decreases from 40 till 100 numbers of epochs showing much better performance, similarly, from **Figure 4.3** and **Figure 4.4**, it is seen that, layer 3 converges at 50 epochs and 70 epochs for PCA-DBN and DWT-PCA-DBN image classifiers respectively.
- (h) Therefore, while comparing the convergence of all three networks with respect to number of epochs and errors occurred, it can be concluded that proposed DWT-PCA-DBM is showing best setting with optimal value of error and epochs.
- (i) As the weight initialization is one of the important factors considered during network initialization and tuning, in this work, three weight initialization ranges have been considered for all three deep learning-based networks.
- (j) For DBN network as shown in **Figure 4.5** initializing the weights of DBN network with all the types of random values results in converging from 40 epochs but experimenting with small random weights results in least error.
- (k) PCA-DBN network as shown in **Figure 4.6** also shows better convergence and less error with respect to initializing the network with small weights.
- (l) Similarly, in proposed DWT-PCA-DBN network shown in **Figure 4.7**, experimenting with small values for weight initialization helps the network with least error, though, it converges at 70 epochs.
- (m) While comparing among all three networks from **Figure 4.8**, it can be concluded that, proposed DWT-PCA-DBN network for image classification is showing outstanding performance with respect to the number epochs and error. DBN network is converging at 40 epochs, while PCA-DBN is at 100 epochs and DWT-

PCA-DBN is 70 epochs with least error in comparison to other two networks.

- (n) Additionally, statistical performance measures have been performed using McNemar's test to validate the significant differences between the different existing and proposed classifier models.

Conclusion

Medical image processing has been expanding its path dramatically and now-a-days this field is also attracting the experts from many other fields of research such as; engineering, mathematics, statistics, biology, computer science etc. Rapid growth in the collection of medical images and their analysis and proper use of those images plays vital role for development of image analysis strategies. Many computational models have been explored and proposed based on MRI, CT and PET images. Considering, the growing interest in the medical image classification, attempts are made in this study to focus on design of accurate classification models using MRI, CT and PET images. The principal idea of this current study is focused on design and validation of computational models which will automate routine, tedious tasks involved in medical image data analysis and can obtain the quantitative values from the images which cannot be measured directly. Those quantitative measures can be used for design and development of digital image classification models with statistical population analysis. Sometimes, radiologists, may miss the points while interpreting the images, therefore, those algorithms can play important role to notify them and they can analyse significant volume of images and can produce high quality information out of those images for disease diagnose and treatment. In this thesis, we have tried to explore the performance and emphasizes on the SVM, ELM and DNN techniques for design of computational models for brain MRI image analysis. The theoretical foundations and statistical validations of SVM, ELM and DNN for medical image classification have been performed.

Considering the importance and utility of the image classification, researchers are working in this field and resulted in extensive research and many approaches for image segmentation based on intensity, color, texture etc. have been proposed. The extensive studies on various medical image processing models for image classification and segmentation have been discussed in second chapter.

In image processing, features have vital role in image processing and before getting the features various pre-processing techniques are applied on the sampled images to resize, denoise and normalize the images and get the quantitative value to be used as input the classification models. The useful features are extracted from the image datasets using data mining or machine learning methodologies. This learning technique helps get the required and relevant features from the images and those extracted features will lead to accurate classification of images. This is the most crucial pre-processing step for any classification algorithm and the performance of the classifier heavily depend on the finding numerical values for those images which are of interest. The first study of this thesis focussed on design of a feature extraction model to detect the brain disorder from brain MRI images based on an integrated form of wavelet DWT. In this work, Haar and Bi-orthogonal 1.3 wavelet functions are used to extract relevant features. Then, extracted features are combined to form a feature matrix and given as input to the SVM classifier. This proposed method has been compared with MLPNN, Naïve Bayesian network and logistic regression. Also this model has been compared with few existing literatures based on this work and additionally, this work has been validated using various accuracy measures. The next work in this thesis have been focussed to design of a hybridized classification model by modifying DWT, ABC and ELM for extracting features, obtaining the optimized parameters for ELM and classifying the image datasets respectively. This proposed MABC-ELM had also been compared with MLPNN, Naïve Bayesian and linear regression techniques.

Deep learning which is an advanced form of ANN is doing justice to all the valuable data in almost all the fields of speech recognition, image processing, natural language processing, financial engineering and health care research. Deep learning can be defined as a class of machine learning algorithm and is a supervised learning approach for data classification and uses some form of gradient descent mechanism for training the model. Deep learning approaches can extract the features from the data automatically to solve the problem of feature extraction through its hierarchical structure. In the last work, an image classification model based on improving the features of DBN and PCA is used to extract the relevant and reduced sized of features respectively. In this work, we have tried to experiment DBN which is composed of stacked RBMs for mining the most significant features from the

reduced feature set layer by layer. Basically, this DBN requires multiple hidden layers with a good number of hidden units to get the best features from the raw pixels of image data leading to increase in complexity of processing with respect to training the models. Therefore, here an attempt has been made to integrate DBN and DWT to lower down the training time for processing the images. This proposed methodology has also been compared with traditional machine learning based non deep learning approaches to get a clear cut idea between both types of learning strategies. Additionally, the proposed method has gone through the McNemar's statistical validation test. Major challenges faced by image analysts is the sheer complexity of the visual task and been mostly ignored by the current approaches. Considering increasing amount of data, we need to develop adjustable, scalable and advanced image processing and visualization algorithms. Additionally, data acquisition being the first and foremost important area of image processing needs to be explored in greater way. the working architecture of this method.

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A Survey on Applications and Performance of Deep Convolution Neural Network Architecture for Image Segmentation

K.Bhargavi^{1,2}, Nethravathi P S², Ch V Phani Krishna¹

¹Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad, Telangana, India – 500097.

²Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Srinivasa University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India – 574146

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3977

1. OVERVIEW

To "depart" an image is to divide it into smaller, more manageable pieces using analytical methods. Partitioning an image into separate regions is a necessary pre-processing step for image analysis leading to object representation, exploration, recognition, dimension, and visualisation; however, care must be taken to eliminate the things or functions of interest that are strongly linked to each region. [1-3] Therefore, segmentation is also known as a technique for grouping pixels that have comparable characteristics. The research demonstrates that a number of different methods may be used for picture division. This picture division facilitates the management of both intermediate and creative photographs. In most cases, the quality of the image segmentation will determine the accuracy of the resulting assessment. Numerous applications need reliable and precise image segmentation tools, including market analysis, optical character identification, objects monitoring, satellite image classification, and the detection, characterization, and size of bone, cells in medical images. [3-5] Once the application's photo department has determined that no more action is necessary, the procedure will end. Several common methods exist for partitioning an image into meaningful parts. Clustering, model fitting, and probabilistic methods, as well as morphological landmarks, are now under investigation. [6-7] Further,

image division can be broadly classified as (a) thresholding-based division, where pie chart thresholding and reducing techniques are applied directly to the image and can also be combined with pre- and post-processing techniques, and (b) shape-based division, where the picture is separated based on the shape of items in the image.

(b) classification based on picture orientation, where edges are used for feature detection;

(e) matching is used to detect a picture that is very similar to another in order to locate the object of interest in a photo [1-5]. (C) area-based division starts with a central point on the item and expands outward to the boundary. Both absence and similarity criteria are used in most image processing methods. The quantum leaps in the strength of the images are used by both the resemblance-based technique and the interruption-based method to divide the image into pieces, which are then combined. [8] In this article, we take a look at convolutional semantic networks (CNNs), also known as deep semantic networks, and how they may be used to segment medical images. In this study, we focused on articles that were published between 2015 and 2017 and discussed the use of deep convolution semantic networks to the problem of picture classification.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2

provides examples of fundamental scientific image processing concepts and their utility; Section 3 details the design and performance of deep CNN, along with the current tasks being performed by deep CNN and their modifications; and Section 4 provides a summary of the paper's findings. The examination of deep CNN-based image processing tasks in Topic 3 has been greeted with an ongoing debate of the aforementioned obstacles, worries noticed, matching datasets, model employed, efficiency, benefits, and future scope. Section 4 is the last section of the paper.

2. MEDICALIMAGESEGMENTATION

The automated detection of cancerous cells in mammograms is only one of the many scientific applications of photo dividing. Calculated tomography (CT) imaging is one of the most frequently used radiography techniques for diagnosis, research, and treatment planning. [3-7] Many scientific images suffer from a low signal-to-noise ratio, making them computationally less clear and trustworthy compared to their digital camera counterparts. For example, ultrasonic images demonstrate how speckle sound reduces the ability to get a definitive conclusion while evaluating medical data. Therefore, a clean image is necessary for precise confirmation and evaluation; this is known as picture division and entails aligning the image's pixels such that their values are consistent despite their relative sizes. After collecting data from two images, you may utilise it to properly integrate useful information from the image of interest. [8] There are a number of methods for identifying brain tumours from brain cells, such as conventional radiology, ultrasonically, magnetic vibration imaging, and computerised tomography, but manually identifying a large number of CT-scan images is time-consuming and prone to error. This has increased the need for completely automated computerised systems, since computer-assisted systems are increasingly employed as a backup for medical professionals in an attempt to minimise errors and mistakes. Therefore, image segmentation is a necessary pre-processing task for noise reduction, improvement of photo quality, and clarity, and this photo division as a pre-handling task becomes the essential task in

the field of clinical image handling in order to develop a reliable representation of brain-images. This picture segmentation and also extra analysis relied heavily on a number of artificial intelligence-based techniques, such as k-means, k-medians, hierarchical and density-based clustering algorithms, and synthetic semantic networks with their different variants. In addition to traditional semantic networks, recent advances in the compatibility and accuracy of other photo division aids for scientific image assessment [9, 10] show promise.

3. DEEP CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK AND IT'S APPLICATION FOR IMAGESEGMENTATION

A CNN, like a semantic network, is made up of many convolution layers and several fully connected ones. Various convolutions are followed by various combinations. After receiving their inputs, neurons in each layer do a dot product, perhaps followed by non-linearity, as part of a typical neural network's inter layer connectivity. However, CNN is a semantic network that uses images and has [11] weight bits in just two dimensions; it is a back-breeding network. A Convolution layer is used as the foundation, followed by a Pooling layer, and finally a Fully-Connected layer. There are a total of [12] degrees, and it's possible that an aeroplane may be located in any one of them. The raw pixel values might be recorded as $m \times r$ picture, where m is the height and width of the image and r is the number of networks, assuming for the moment that CNN's inputs are photographs. In the case of a red, green, and blue image, $r = 3$. The convolution layer has k filters of dimensions $n \times p$, where n must be less than the image size and p 's dimension may be equal to or less than r . This is the layer where the results of neuron addition to input regions are calculated. The element-sensible activation feature is then triggered using a $\text{limit}(0, x)$ threshold set to no . The down-tasting algorithms and spatial measurements (width, height) of the pooling layer reduce the number of measurements required for a given volume, and the final course scores are computed by the fully connected layer. Convolution transforms the initial image layer into the final scores for a certain class in this precise way. CNN's awareness of the geographical origin of the [13] inputs is not

3978

a separate factor.

With its meticulous classification of the issue location in the second stage of the analysis process, CNN has extraordinary efficacy in many domains, especially in clinical information images [14]. In fact, it is able to recognise almost any kind of condition pattern. CNN is easier to train than other networks because to its fewer requirements and fewer links, but using it on a large scale for high-resolution images is costly despite its widespread acclaim in the local community. Using a VPU to accelerate the execution of 2D convolution and other common training-related

processes is one way that deep convolutional neural networks get around this issue [15].

Deep knowing, a method of calculating models that benefits from a pecking order of higher-order features acquired from simpler ones, has recently attracted the attention of scientists working in the area of artificial semantic networks (ANNs). These models, also known as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), combine linear and nonlinear data to swiftly identify and also create a model from high-level information, therefore automating the formerly manual process of attribute production.

Figure1: Structure of Convolution Neural Network (CNN)

on the basis of firsthand accounts [16-32] In light of CNN's computational might, Xiaohong W. Gao et al. [16] proposed classifying CT brain pictures into ad and balanced groups using a non-supervised automated version of CNN. After segmenting CT images into commercial, unpleasant (tumour), and usual categories, we suggest a novel CNN design that combines 2D and 3D CNN. The combined CNN design has recorded accuracy's of 85.2%, 80%, and 95.3% for these three classes, with an average accuracy of 87.6%. Recent work by Xiaohong W. Gao et al. [17] suggests a number of deep-understanding integrated solutions for cardiograph categorization. Two convolutional semantic networks (CNNs) trained on the same data but in distinct spatial and temporal directions are

combined in their suggested network design. First, the temporal CNN pre-processes all the photographs before training/learning begins; next, the optical circulation is used twice to acquire the speed and velocity of the photos; and lastly, the spatial CNN uses the protected images to uncover spatial information.

For the purpose of image classification, Shuchao Discomfort et al. [18] created a fully-automated classifier based on domain-name-moved deep convolutional semantic networks (CNN). When used to the categorization of clinical images, the proposed domain-transferred deep convolutional neural networks (DT-DCNN) achieved excellent results. The authors' novel notion of employing straightforward information augmentation based on categorization greatly

improved the effectiveness of this CNN-based hybridised version. Cecilia S. Lee et al. have published a service that automatically evaluates images taken from electronic medical records (EMRs) using deep semantic networks and machine learning techniques. [19] In a study comparing Optical Coherence Tomography scans of people with and without age-related Macaulay degeneration, researchers showed that deep learning may be used to identify those with AMD. New convolutional semantic networks for classifications that use the Xavier method to initialise their weights have been proposed. Multiple models have been trained on 100 set-dimensional images at a knowledge cost of 0.001 using the stochastic slope descent optimisation. Five hundred distinct deep semantic network designs were recorded in action, and their performance was evaluated using a cross-recognition with acknowledgment efficiency test. The network has identified the crucial regions of the Optical Comprehensibility Tomography images, and the screening may reveal the potential attributes to identify AMD images from conventional images.

Wei Shen et al. [20] studied the classification of CT images using a machine learning based style they called the Multi-crop Convolutional Semantic Network (MC-CNN) to cut different regions from convolutional feature maps without using division to develop multi-sale functions and also used on a computationally efficient single network. Finding the questionable information and spotting it using a set of discriminatory features derived from a learned neural network was the focus of this study. The authors tackle the central difficulty of making a picture area consisting of both the healthy cells and furthermore, some questionable faults at unique levels by exploring the capabilities of deep understanding style in an integrated style termed MC-CNN.

The use of a deep knowing approach that rapidly mines discriminatory aspects for understanding has been suggested by John Arevalo et al. for clinical identification of breast cancer cells in mammography. [21] The proposed deep learning approach consists of two phases: the first enhances image quality through preprocessing the pictures, and the second uses a

monitored training technique to classify the images. Before undergoing information improvement, global and local comparison normalisation, and eventually artificial intelligence of discriminatory characteristics using a convolutional semantic network (CNN), images are chopped in the pre-processing step.

Researchers have also found that the considerable spatial and architectural variability of swellings makes it difficult to automate the separation of CT images into individual lumps. To address this issue, Lin Huang et al. developed a CT picture assistance department that employs numerous closely monitored CNN. [22] It is a three-layer multi-scale function-discovery strategy that incorporates both local and global picture information, in addition to a pre-processing step that minimises differences across images. Pre-processing processes have already been completed, such as photo intensity normalisation and focal aircraft location. The picture was then refined using a stop design to extract a fractional map, and a pre-trained model was converted to a fully convolutional form using just CNN. The suggested architecture has been quantitatively compared using the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Average Sensitivity (AS), Normal Hammoude Range (AHD), and F1-measure. Jeremy Kawahara et al. [23] created a BrainNetCNN variant based on a convolution network to predict redevelopment using Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) of newborns between 7 and 46 weeks. The authors suggested employing edge-to-edge, edge-to-node, and node-to-graph convolution filters to get rid of the topological part of the architectural thinking network. Each filter takes as inputs all of the function maps from the layer before it, and utilises them to generate a function map for the next layer. The edge-to-edge layer functions as a base layer in a convolutional network, filtering information at the edge nodes. An edge-to-node filter, using the adjacency matrix from each quality map, uses a combination of the inbound and outbound weights. A strong function is one having a significant weight. This filter aggregates the actions of neighbouring edges into a collection of node answers to produce a single response from all the nodes in the graph, much how the node-to-graph layer collapsed the node's

dimensional into a single scalar per-attribute map. The authors of this study demonstrated the effectiveness of the suggested architecture by proactively meeting the needs of each scenario via the use of deep learning.

Tumours may develop in any part of the brain and range significantly in size, shape, colour, and other characteristics. For this reason, artificial intelligence (AI)-based methods have lately been investigated as a potential cure to the challenge of segmenting these brain pictures. Taking into account the potential of a deep semantic network or a CNN Mohammad Havaeiet al. [24] developed a novel CNN architecture that takes into account both regional and global contexts. Instead of a conventional CNN, they have employed the last layer of a convolutional network. Their solution employs a two-stage training method to even out the discrepancy between tags for individual chunks of a course. A brain image may now be hectorated in between 25 seconds and 3 minutes with this completely automated version. The two-stage training procedure given by the suggested two-path style is a more effective solution to the tag imbalance issue in information streams. DICE, sensitivity analysis, and the originality index have all been used to evaluate the efficacy of the recommended falls design.

Wenlu Zhang et al. [25] used a deep convolutional semantic network (Deep-CNN) to segment images of the baby brain into white matter, grey matter, and cerebrospinal fluid for the study of disease and health. Some authors have proposed using deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to partition iso-intense layers of cortical circuitry. These networks are multi-layered, fully trainable versions that can detect highly nonlinear mappings between inputs and outputs. Several shock layers have been proposed for CNN, and it has been shown via analysis of the cleared regions that the spots from the cells are not constant.

Forensic dentistry is another area where Deep CNN has proven useful. To properly tape the dental information, it may be useful to use the outcomes of a computer model based on Deep-CNN for dental identification, post-mortem dental discoveries, and teeth concerns from an oral graph, as suggested by Yuma Mikia et al. [26] The

authors of this study classified teeth in oral CT images using Deep-CNN. Initially, CT scans were mined for interesting regions to use as training data for the network. Authors have mostly looked at how well random sampling works for both training and assessment. We do the computations using an AlexNet that is built up of 5 convolution layers, 3 merging layers, and a complete set of connection layers. The effects of four different resizing techniques (plant, squash, fill, and 50% plant half fill) were compared using images with manually clipped areas of interest that were resized and randomly cut again for exploration. We were able to determine the accuracy of the classification to be 93.5% with the use of data augmentation. Pavle Prenticeic and company of writers.

27] employed this Deep-CNN to study the consequences of diabetic retinopathy on customers. Before feeding the fondus images into the Deep-CNN, a denoising method called full variation was used to reduce the amount of noise present in the images. Next, a convolutional neural network (CNN) with a series of convolutional, max pooling completely connected layers is applied to the raw pixel strengths of the original image to generate a new feature vector for classification.

Using a Deep-CNN based feature discovery approach, as shown by Jun Xu et al., histological images may be automatically split into Epithelial and Stromal cells. [28] Deep-CNN, which consists of two sets of convolution layers that alternate, maxpooling, two link layers, and a final group layer, is suggested in this study. In order to avoid overly-optimized parameters, this network was trained using a coarse-to-fine move method. A SVN classifier called LIBSVM has been constructed using the Gaussian Kernel and 10-fold cross-validation. Sensitivity analysis and AUC curves are used to determine the effectiveness of the suggested design in comparison to 9 state-of-the-art Deep-CNN based designs. Xipeng Pana et al. [29] employed the Deep-CNN to segment the centres of pathological images. There are three steps to this process: first, diseased documents are cleaned of background noise using sparse reconstruction; second, cell cores are

fractionalized using a Deep-CNN trained using a waterfall of convolution networks; and third, a cell's nucleus is extracted using the same method. Once the developer has been trained using input patches with their corresponding class tags, the randomly selected sick images are generated. The Aid Vector Machine, the k-nearest neighbour method, and the k-means algorithm are only some of the models that have been compared to this one.

In order to quickly dissect the neuroanatomy in T1-weighted MRI data, Christian Wachinger et al. has proposed using a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) named DeepNAT. [30] The suggested multitasking model takes into consideration not just the facility voxel of the set, but also the surrounding ones. This study not only employs a foreground/background split, but also 2 purchased networks to recognise foreground mental structures, so fixing the previously untested training course inconsistency problem. After three convolutional layers including pooling, set normalisation, and non-linearities, this DeepNAT employs fully linked layers. Parallel processing for rapid training, hierarchical division to tell foreground from background, and the inclusion of ghostly collaborators as a criteria for retaining context information in patches are all investments kept under wraps. Comparisons have been made between the proposed DeepNAT and two state-of-the-art methods, PICSL and STAPLE.

3. DISCUSSION/RESEARCH CHALLENGES/OVERALL PERFORMANCE/OBSERVATIONS

Research-ers	Datasets used	Technique Applied	Overall Performance	Observations
Xiaohong W.Gao <i>etal.</i>	285 dataset of 3D are collected from Navy General Hospital, China, which compose 57, 115 and 113 data respectively in the category of Alzheimer's, lesion and normal	Deep Neural Network/CNN	The fusion of this CNN model has reported the accuracy of 85.2%, 80% and 95.3% respectively for AD lesion (tumour) and normal and advanced CNN architecture integrating 2D and 3D CNN	Application of deep learning neural network compromises with the largest number of datasets and also the data imbalance problem needs to be addressed and the better accuracy can be observed if we have more balanced data
Xiaohong W.Gao <i>etal.</i>	432 ultrasonic video images of echocardiography from Tsinghua University Hospital at Beijing and Fuzhou University Hospital at Fuzhou, China. These data contain eight view classes captured from 93	Fused Deep Learning/CNN	Without using acceleration of temporal information, proposed work outperforms all the hand-crafted approaches with 89.5% precision rate	This fused CNN/Deep network integrated model is both automatic and selective for classification of echocardiography images from videos and the proposed two-strand network shows classification

3983

(contd...Table)

Research-ers	Datasets used	Technique Applied	Overall Performance	Observations
	patients aged between 7 and 85 years old comprising of 35 with motion abnormalities and 58 normal cases			accuracy upto 92.1% and is the best so far the literature is concerned.
Shuchao Pang <i>etal.</i>	Three well-known public biomedical image databases such as; NEMA-CT, TCIA-CT and OASIS-MRI database	Domain Transfer Deep Neural Network (DT-DCNN)	Proposed method obtained accuracy of 100% for NEMA-CT and TIA-CT datasets and 93.76% for OASIS-MRI dataset	This method can effectively deal with limited number of labelled biomedical images with deep learning and transfer learning
Cecilia S.	2.6 million OCT images of 43	Deep	Accuracy at image level, the	The application of occlusion

Lee	328 macular OCT scans from 9285 patients. After linking the macular OCT scan to the E-MR, 48312 images from 4392 normal OCT scans and 52690 images from 4790 AMD OCT scans were reselected. 80839 images used for training and 20163 images for testing or validation.	Learning	ROC curve of 92.78% with an accuracy of 87.63%. At the macula level, ROC curve of 93.83% with an accuracy of 88.98%. At a patient level, ROC curve of 97.45% with an accuracy of 93.45%. Peaks sensitivity and specificity with optimal cutoffs were 92.64% and 93.69%, respectively	testing provides insight into the trained deep learning model and which features were most important in distinguishing AMD images from normal images. This study has included only images from patients whom the author's study criteria, and the neural network was only trained on these images and they did not exclude images with poor quality
Wei Shen <i>et al.</i>	LIDC-IDRI dataset consisting of 1010 patients with lung cancer thoracic CT scans as well as mark-up annotated lesions	Multi-crop Convolutional Neural Network (MC-CNN)	Classification accuracy (87.14%) and the AUC score (0.93)	The extracted deep features from the proposed methodology can be considered to be integrated with conventional image features to further improve the precision performance
John Arvalo <i>et al.</i>	The datasets are extracted from Breast Cancer Digital Repository (BCDR). The dataset was built from 344 breast cancer patients' cases containing a total of 736 film mammography views with 426 benign lesions and 310 malignant lesions	CNN	The increasing performance has been observed 0.826 in terms of AUC and the Wilcoxon test hypothesis evaluated $p < 0.1$	This model used a combination of image-based features with additional segmentation information and this combination improved the performance results especially it helps to augment the performance of the hand-crafted representation.
Lin Huang <i>et al.</i>	405 test images (109 bone lesions osteosarcoma CT images and 296 mixed lesions osteosarcoma CT images)	Fully CNN	DSC of 87.80%, AS of 86.88% HM of 19.81%, F1-measure of 0.9080	Limitations observed for segmentation of small tumor regions being not sensitive to the small details of images and the output contains some vague results due to the large p -sample stride. This can be handled by using more convolutional layers.
Jeremy Kawahara <i>et al.</i>	168 DTI images from a cohort of infants born very preterm and scanned between 27 and 45	BrainNet CNN	Absolute error of age prediction was correlated with $r = 0.224$, implying that age predictions	Connections from the premotor and primary motor cortices were found to be predictive of

(contd...Table)

Research-ers	Datasetsused	Technique sApplied	OverallPerformance	Observations
	weekspostmenstrualage		weremoreaccurateforyoung erinfants	bettermotoroutcomes.
Havaei et al.	Fully-annotated MIC CAI segmentation challenge2013datasetusingt hewelldefinedtrainingandte stingsplits	CNN-DNN	The time neededtosegmentanentireb rain variesbetween25secondsan d3minutes,makingthem practical segmentationmethods	Thismethodhasbeenevaluat ed by BRATS 2013online evaluation system andconfirmsits performanceandthe two-pathway model alsoachieves good result when the datadistributionisunbala nced.
WenluZhangetal.	AcquiredT1, T2,anddiffusionweighted MR images of 10healthyinfantsusingaSiem ens3TheadonlyMRscanner	Deep-CNN	DICERatiohas been appliedtoquantitativelymea surethesegmentation accuracyandalsothestatistic alsignificancehasbeen performed using Wilcoxonsignedranktests	The strategy worked well tofindthepatches butithasbeenobservedthat,t henumberofpatchesarenoti mbalanced,whichcanbehan dledbysamplingensemble learningstrategies
YumaMik iaetal.	Two dental CT units, namelyVeraviewepocs 3D (J.MoritaMfg,Corp.,Kyoto,Ja pan)andAlphard VEGA (AsahiRoentgenInd. Co.,Ltd.,Kyoto,Japan),which wereusedtoacquireimagesin 33and19cases	Deep-CNN	Classification accuracy obtai-ned 80% without segmentationand by increasing the numberof training samples by rotationand intensity transformationaccuracy of 91.0% was achi-eved	Deeplearningin generalisconsideredtorequi re alargenumberoftrainingsam plesbutinthiswork,despitet helimitednumberofcases,th epromisingaccuracyhasbee nobserved.Duetoconvolutio nwith the pooling process, thismethodisrobustenought oautomatically, shift the image,recognizedand classifytoothtype.
PavlePr entašice tal.	DRiDB which contains 50 colorfundusimagesforwhicha llthemain structures like bloodvessels,opticdiskandm aculaare marked along with patholo-gicalchanges	Deep-CNN	Foreachimage,thenumbero ftruepositives(TP),falseposi -tives(FP) andfalsenegatives(FN)are0. 78,0.78and0.78 respectively.	Deep- CNNhasbeeneffectivelyuse dtosegmentationin colorfondusphotographsan dithasbeenobservedthat,thi sworkcanbeenhancedbyad dingsomemorepreandpost processingstepsandalsoaddi ngsomehighlevelfeaturesfo rfinaalsegmentation.

3985

JunXu <i>etal.</i>	<i>Dataset:</i> NetherlandsCancerInstitut e(NKI)andVancouverGener alHospital (VGH).Itconsistsof157recta ngularimageregions(106NK I,51VGH) <i>DatasetII:</i> Helsinki University Central Hospitalfrom1989to1998.D 2com-prises27TMAs ofcolorectalcaner	Deep-CNN	ThisDeep- CNNbasedapproachyieldsap erfectresult(100%)interms of TruePositiveRate(TPR),True NegativeRate(TNR),Positive PredictiveValue (PPV), Negative Pred-ictive Value (NPV), Accuracy(ACC),F1Score(F1), andMatthewsCorrelationCo efficient(MCC)	Proposedarchitectureuses adeeparchitectureto learncomplexfeatures in adata- drivenfashionandithassho wn improved classificationaccuracyobtai nedviahandcraftedfeatures
XipengPa <i>naetal.</i>	58HematoxylinandEosin(H &E) histopathology imagesofbreast tissuefromYale,	Deep-CNN	Accuracy (ACC), precision(P),recall (R), and F1-measure (F1)	First,thesparsereconstructi onwith K-SVD and Batch- OMP algorithmsareused toenhance ce

(contd...Table)

Research- Datasetsused	Techniques Observationsers	OverallPerformance	Applied
DavidRimm’sLaboratory,with 2benignand26malignant CNNwithcularcell/people/david_rimm. finally,profile		metricsandalsothreecommonlythenucleusarearemove3 usedsegmentation methods backgroundandthen,theimagesrespectively. http:// segmentationhasbeengonemedicine.yale.edu/bbs/mole andWatershed-basedwere usingDeep- applied to the dataset to producestuctural labels and thebaselineperformancesfor morphologicaloperationswith comparisonpurposes	somepriorknowledgehas been introduced to improve thesegmentationperforman ce
Christian Wachin MRIgera <i>et al.</i> Warfield,2012), whichconsists risontoDeepNAT(p<0.001),scans.It evolvedthroughthree ofT1-weightedMRiscans taskfrom30subjectsofOASIS	DeepNAT	DeepNATcrfyieldssignificantlyhigherDICEScoresincompa- FreeSurfer (p< 0.001),and STAPLE(p<0.001),whereaslearning,hierarchical thedifferencetoPICS (p=0.06)is y	Authorsproposeda3DDeep- CNN for segmentation of mainphasessuchas;multi- segmentation,spectral notsignificant. coordinates,and3Dfull connectedconditionalrando

mfield. Further this work can be improved by increasing the amount of training data, progresses in GPU and also structural and methodological advances in deep CNN.

4. CONCLUSION

The computer scientist has a challenging problem in the automatic division of CT pictures, ultrasonic video clips of cardiograph images, OCT images, and brain development for the diagnosis of cancer cells. Researchers have access to a wealth of publicly accessible datasets on which to test, refine, and evaluate their preferred approaches to picture segmentation. First, this article sketches out the generally accepted practises for managing clinical photographs. Our focus is on the most recent work in this field from 2015-2017, and we have made an effort to understand the deep convolution neural network and its applications in picture segmentation for clinical images in particular. There has been significant growth in the development of new technologies in the field of medical image processing, and there is still a great deal of unattended research, which will undoubtedly encourage the looks to explore new technologies for accurate identification, discovery, medical diagnosis, and expedition of pictures for clinical area.

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Deep Learning Neural Networks for Object Recognition and Contour Tracking-Bases Knowledge Extraction

K.Bhargavi^{1,2}, Nethravathi P S², Ch.V.PhaniKrishna¹

¹Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad, Telangana, India-500097.

²Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Institute of Engineering & Technology, Srinivasa University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India-574146.

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Abstract—Using spectral or syntactic domain pattern recognition algorithms, objects are recognised in digital photographs. In order to recognise items that would otherwise go undetected and latent, quicker, more accurate, and smarter pattern recognition techniques must be developed due to the constantly growing volume of data gathered by digital picture collecting systems. Using cryptic learning neural networks for object recognition is one such endeavour. Knowledge that was gathered from the outlines of different objects that were present in a digital picture served as the input to this system. In order to recognise things using a neural network and extract information about the delineations of different items and constituents of a digital picture, this study proposes a unique technique.

Keywords—cryptic Learning, Object Extraction, (MI) Machine Intelligence, Pattern Recognition

I. PREFACE

Entity in a digital photograph is essentially pixels array that have been geometrically arranged to get its shape. To investigate the shape of an object, a 3x3 neighbourhood can serve as a fundamental construction element. This means that any item can be depicted via this 3x3 structural block and its categories, which can then be geographically dispersed as necessary. In order for a digital image to be interpretable, its components must be spatially dispersed and their relationships must be visually apparent. For example, a depiction of an airport is only comprehensible if it depicts an administrative tower, asphalt, runway, and a couple of buildings with regular shapes. It is conceivable to visualise these objects and conclude that the seriesting is an airport. Computers equipped with heuristics-based algorithms are also capable of producing identical outcomes. In a strictly technical context, this is known as machine learning. As computerised depictions of the human being neural network, neural networks are shows a crucial role in machine(ML) learning.

A neural network's fundamental inputs consist of 0s and 1s or lexicographic sequences of these symbols. Any word or visual pattern can be expressed via 0s and 1s, which can then be utilised to instruct a neural network to reach a conclusion. This piece aims to assist readers in gaining a better understanding of the contours of different items and in encoding the directional traits as an information vector. Thus, a thing can be represented as a vector of information, which is transmitted through a neural system for item identification..

II. KNOWLEDGE VECTORS AND CONTOURS OF ITEMS

The subsequent stages are used to gather the information vector of a contour. A contouring algorithm of your choosing is applied to an object to begin. Figure 1 illustrates a model picture and also contours which depicts 16 convex designs built in 3x3. In a similar fashion, 240 additional Designs can be derived from the Design A shown in Fig. 1(b). Thus, the 3X3 matrix of the vertices could generate the complete series of 256 Designs. These Designs are shown in Figure 2. One can create a vector of information for each of these 256 Designs. These information vectors fundamentally depict the monitoring orientations for contours. Tracking contours are performed in a circular direction. A contour track is a collection of trajectory instruction and dimension pairings.

Fig.1 Designs, contours, and convex Designs in the 3x3 neighbourhood are provided as examples.

Fig.2 displays each of the 240 Designs in a 3x4 neighbourhood.

Fig.2(a): Design series #1

Fig.2(b):Designseries#2

Fig.2(b):Designseries#3

Fig.2(b):Designseries#4

Fig.2(b):Designseries #5

Fig.2(b):Designseries #6

Fig.2(b):Designseries #7

Fig.2(b):Designseries #8

Directions Coding

According to Table 1, each direction of a digitised matrix is encoded. Table 1: knowledge code collection

Directions	Directional Code	Semantics	Sample Patterns	Knowledge Code
R	R	Right direction	A	R-D-L-U
DR	DR	Down towards right	B2	DR-UR-D-L-U
D	D	Down	B4	R-D-L-UR-UL
DL	DL	Down left	B6	R-DL-DR-L-U
L	L	Left	B8	R-D-UL-DR-U
UL	UL	Upper left	C2,4	DR-UR-D-L-UR
U	U	Upper	C2,6	DR-UR-DL-DR-L-U
UR	UR	Upper right	C2,8	DR-UR-D-UL-DL-U

Consider an illustration and implement this idea to it.

Figure 3 depicts an example image

(a)triangle sample (b)Contourtriangle

fig3:Triangle Sampleimagewith contour

Extraction of Knowledgevector:Fig.3(b):

{<75,121>/D1*DR2*D1*DR3*R1*DR1*D1*DR3*D1*DR3*1*DR7*D1*DR5*D1*DR2*D1*DR3*R1*DR2*D1*DR1*D1*DR2*DR4*D2*DR2*R1*DR4*D2*DR7*D2*DR1*R1*DR5*D1*DR1*D1*DR8*D1*DR4*D1*DR3*D1*DR3*R1*DR1*D1*DR3*D1*DR2*L175*UR3*U1*UR2*U1*UR2*R1*UR3*U1*UR2*U1*UR7*D1*U2*UR7*U2*UR5*R1*UR1*U1*UR2*U1*UR4*U1*UR7*U1*UR5*U1*UR1*U1*UR4*R1*UR3*U2*UR7*U2*UR1*R1*UR5*U1*UR2*U1*UR4*U1*UR1*R1*UR2*U1*UR2*/<77,120>#}

Networker can restrict the knowledge vector to a particular instance of eight directions:

{<75,121>/R10*DR82*D24*L175*U22*UR82*/<77,120>#}

Standardisation of the information

vector{DR116*L175*UR104}

Vector code normalised to 100 pixels

{DR29*L44*UR26}

III. NEURALNETWORKFOROBJECTRECOGNITION

The design of a neural network utilising an information vector in Fig. 4 is shown for object identification in a digital picture.

fig. 4: Fundamental Neural network architecture

Figure 4 depicts the initialization of the neural network's weights to arbitrary values. During the feed-forward stage, every neuron in the input unit \$x_i\$ and hidden unit \$z_1\$ through \$z_p\$ perceives and transmits an input signal. Every unit in the concealed layer performs the computation and subsequently transmits the resulting value, \$z_j\$, to the neurons situated in the output layer. The output unit utilizes the activation function \$y_k\$ to calculate the comprehensive solution \$ss\$ for a specific input Design. This is the typical operational mechanism of neural networks. During the backpropagation process, the neurons in each outcome unit undertake a comparison between their calculated activation \$y_k\$ and the target value \$t_k\$ as a means of estimating the error for a given design. The error is utilised to dispense the error at the output level \$y_k\$ uniformly among all segments in the preceding tier. Each clandestine entity \$z_j\$ is also associated with a corresponding factor \$\delta_j\$.

Likewise, the factor \$j\$ is calculated for each concealed unit \$z_j\$. To update weights, the weight correction terms \$\Delta W_{ij}\$ and \$\Delta W_{jk}\$ are computed and added to the old weighted value. The procedures are provided below:

Parameters

\$x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n)\$- Input vector

\$t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k, \dots, t_m)\$- Output vector

δ_k =outputunit error
 δ_j =hiddenunit error
 α =learningratio
 v_{ij} =loadsofinputlayer
 v_{oj} =bionsonconcealed unit
 z_j =concealedunit activation
 w_{jk} = weights of hidden
 w_{ok} =outputunitbios k
 y_k =activation outputk

Procedure

1. Make the weights' initial values modest and random.
2. Take actions from steps 3 to 10 while the halting false condition.
3. Carry out steps 4 to 10 for every drill pair.
4. Obtains the input signal for each input $x_i(i=1, \dots, n)$ and delivers it to whole units in the concealed layer $z_j(j=1, \dots, p)$.
5. Everyconcealed unit z_j adds itsloaded inputsignals

$$z_{-in j} = v_{oj} + \sum_{i=1}^n x_i v_{ij}$$

and bore upon its activation task

$$z_j = f(z_{-in j})$$

and sends this signal to whole units in the output layer $y_k(k=1, \dots, m)$.

6. Single output $y_k(k=1, \dots, m)$ sums its loaded input signs

$$y_{-in k} = w_{ok} + \sum_{j=1}^p z_j w_{jk}$$

and enter its activation function to compute output signals

$$y_k = f(y_{-in k})$$

7. Respectively, output's unit y_k obtains a target shape t_k matching to an input Design and estimates the error as

$$\delta_k = (t_k - y_k) f'(y_{-in k})$$

8. The error data is estimated as,

$$\delta_j = \sum_{k=1}^m \delta_k w_{jk} f'(y_{-in k})$$

9. Single output unit y_k informs its differences and loads. The alteration is marked by $\Delta w_{jk} = \alpha \delta_k z_j$

And the difference correction equation marked by $\Delta w_{ok} = \alpha \delta_k$.

Therefore, $w_{jk} (new) = w_{jk} (old) + \Delta w_{jk}$ and

$$w_{ok} (new) = w_{ok} (old) + \Delta w_{ok}$$

10. The concealed unit z_j appraises its differences and loads. The load correction span is defined as $\Delta v_{ij} = \alpha \delta_j x_i$ and the difference correction equation is $\Delta v_{oj} = \alpha \delta_j$.

11. Therefore, $v_{ij} (new) = v_{ij} (old) + \Delta v_{ij}$ and

$$v_{oj} (new) = v_{oj} (old) + \Delta v_{oj}$$

12. Test the halting condition

Vectorized normalised codes are used to train neural networks. By normalising the input vector and comparing it to a stored vector, the neural network is tested by

feeding it a test vector at the input layer. By minimising error and categorising the item in accordance with the relevant thresholds, neural networks determine the object.

Fig.5: Neural networks for item identification

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS

The present research paper presents a unique approach for object recognition and knowledge extraction based on contour tracking utilising cryptic learning neural networks. The idea has been put to the test on a variety of photographs, as well as the precision with which it can detect any kind of object—geometric or amorphous. The whole idea was created for pictures that were shown in a rectangular pixel lattice. Alternately, one may use the same technique to pictures that are shown as a hexagonal pixel lattice. The benefit would be that a picture would have superior curvilinear qualities when displayed in a hexagonal lattice

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IoT Based Smart Grid on Smart Cities

Ch. Phani Krishna¹, K. Bhargavi², Dr. Nethravathi³

^{1, 2} Dept of Computer Science and Engineering Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Telangana, India.
phanik16@gmail.com, bhargavi.mtech@gmail.com, velancse@gmail.com

³Institute of Engineering and Technology, Mukka Campus Srinivas University, Mysore, India

Abstract—Smart grid is the supporting features of the smart town or city model. It is energy utilization observing and the management system. Smart grid depends on the communication between the supplier and the customer. Internet of Things based smart grid is a progress of the accessible power grid. Advancement in rapid communication and low-price sensor combined with the expanded sending of the progressed furnish utilities with better data to deal with the grid. Smart grid and IoT are two technologies that turned out to be profoundly grown of late. In the viewpoint of power save, the smart grid is an outstanding result for improving the power utilization though the IoT can be a solution to offers purchasers the ease of having an ongoing strategy to manage and monitoring power utilize in a house. IoT encourages Smart grid to help different system network works all through the generation, transmission, utilization, and sharing of power by incorporating IoT devices, (for example, actuators, and sensors), just as by giving the availability, mechanization and following for such tools and devices. In this paper, propose the design about a smart grid system power generation, transmission, distribution, consumption design based concerning IoT for a challenge in the system configuration and security analysis.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Smart Grid, Sensors

INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things is presently the talk of every city. It witnessed a tremendous growth in every sector. IoT is connected cars, medical devices, street to smart grids for energy management. When we converse about energy management, smart grid is the first thing to appear. Internet of Things can play a significant role in developing smart grids which eventually leads to energy saving. In spite of the fact that the electric network is viewed as a building wonder, we are extending its interwoven nature to its ability. To push ahead, we need another sort of electric network, one that is developed from the base to deal with the groundswell of advanced and electronic gear and innovation reliant on it and one that can robotize and deal with the expanding multifaceted nature and necessities of power in the further feature.

Internet of Things empowered smart grids are more about the energy proficiency and the maintaining of energy utilization at the most reduced expense. Consistently we experience articles incorporate the electronic gadgets as well as the results of higher technological improvement, for example, vehicles and tools yet things that we don't customarily consider as electronic at all such as food and clothing. The "things" of this present reality will coordinate into the virtual world, empowering whenever, anyplace connectivity.

The quantity of regular physical objects and devices associated with the Internet was around 12.5 billion in 2010. The number of values expected to twofold to 25 billion out of 2015 as the number of more smart devices per individual increments to the extent to a further 50 billion by 2020 IoT is a model and a paradigm that thinks about unavoidable nearness in nature of a variety of things and questions that throughout wired and wireless connected and unique tending to plans can connect with one another and participate with different things/items to make new applications and services and arrive at common goals. The aim of the IoT is to allow things to be associated whenever, wherever, with anyone and anything preferably utilizing any network and any service.

1. Smart Grid (SG) and Internet of Things (IoT)

The smart grid there is electric stream as of the power producing to the end user, which is the major flow of the traditional power grid. In the goal of the smart grid the electric stream could be two ways, anywhere the customer will purchase and could likewise sell power. Data flow a enormous scale two-way correspondence flow between the various shareholder and parts of the SG. The majority of the correspondence flow is because of the huge utilization of actuators and other smart objects nearby the transmission and distribution zones, in addition the utilization of smart meters and other smart apparatuses, electric vehicles, and so on. toward the end-user side. The clever power grid, could be viewed while the biggest instantiation of the IoT arrange in the following future. The total power grid, as of the power production toward the power buyers home, industrialized units, street lightning, smart appliances, and so on, include power producing, power transmission and power distribution systems, will be loaded up with intelligence and both-way correspondence abilities to observe and manage the power grid anyplace, at a well granularity and a high precision [1]. For example, smart homes, will be furnished with smart meters and appliances, though power production and power transmission and power distribution systems will be tools through different sensors The aim of the SG is to be a constant power production and power consumption by permitting a fine-grained observing and manage over the power sequence, because of the large various the both-ways conveying smart items, sensors, smart machines, etc.

IoT is a novel idea, on which Internet evolve as of concerning machines and people groups towards interfacing smart objects. Consequently, we can speak that IoT interchanges be the increase of M2M communications. As indicated by Cisco, by 2020 their determination be more than 50 billion associated objects against a populace of 7 billion. An object can be any devices tools implanted with computation, stockpiling and storage and communication with different limits sensor, actuator, mobile phone, etc. While smart objects are as of now connected through exclusive non-IP solution in different applications like a Wireless HART, Z-Wave, IoT aim interfacing the objects at a huge scale using IP-based measures TCP and UDP, IP, etc., through passages if IP support is not probable, while enabling them to connect with some other communicating gathering on or over the Internet. The term IoT regularly make reference to the combination of objects, for example, sensors, RFID, actuators labels or any devices including a conveying interface and a figuring capacity, into the Internet. Objects of the physical world refrigerator, radiator, clothes washer, etc., Could now be effectively available, reasonable and communicate through Internet. Industrial and smart homes have a few applications and some type of sustainable power resource. These machines and assets can be considered as IoT technology. Every can transfer and download information and directions from utilities and home owners. What's more, the grid everywhere has numerous gadgets that can be considered as IoT items, for example, recloses, switches, capacitor banks, transformers, smart sensors, IEDs. When all is said in done, smart grids for countries can have a great many home apparatuses and a huge number of grid devices.

Smart grid is another and current power grid, which is exceptionally, incorporated with cutting edge sensor estimation technology, data and communication technology, and investigation of the decision-making technology, automatic control innovation, energy power technology and grid infrastructures. Compare with the conventional grid, smart grid has been improved clearly in the optimization of power control, the adaptability of grid structure;

optimize the allotment of assets, and improving the power nature of services. Along these lines, smart grid has numerous attributes including strong, self- curative, similarity, integration and optimization, etc. [5]. Internet of Things, specifically "the Internet where the things associated with one another", is the augmentation and extension of Internet-based system. As per the concurred conventions, with IOT key technologies: RFID, sensor innovation, smart technology and nanotechnology, the communication data can be exchange, and the canny acknowledgment, situating, following, checking and the management can be achieved.

Fig 1: IoT based on smart grid

Power Production zone made out of an associated of atomic nuclear, solar or sunlight based, coal, hydro power and wind plant. Transmission Domain manages by vast several of system working areas and substations, a huge different power lines deliver the power to distribution area. Distribution area total of complex systems topologies conveys electrical power to housing areas, metro regions, rural farms, and industrial area for consumption [7]. Software design. In the software of the system is composed of IoT software and WSN software. Both of them are modified software developed and installed in the coordinator nodes, sensor nodes, applications and server.

2. IoT Based Power Generation

The objective for power production is to achieve moderateness, accessibility, supportability and reduce the utilization of fossils and emissions. Many associations like GE, over the world are increasingly utilizing on IoT to accomplish these goals. There are three primary areas where IoT can be Impactful in Power generation. Remote Asset Monitoring and Management This is most likely one of the finest identified uses of IoT in industrial and home applications. Connected sensors are being uses to measure wear, tear, vibration, temperature, and different parameters to decide the general strength of benefits from turbines to transmission lines.

Trends in the information got from sensors could be utilized to estimate the time to failure of key infrastructures and plan support, reducing downtime time because of unscheduled maintenance and help maintain a strategic distance from the financial outcomes of such downtimes. Adopt IoT in power generations could likewise help recognize security issues like gas spillages before they cause harm to laborers and equipment, for the majority element helping stations achieve new protection levels. Procedure Optimization IoT can give constant data about the general condition of the entire generation station and this is incredibly helping plant automation. Real-time data is being utilized to fine-tune the activities of plants, expanding energy transformation from fuels and diminishing the costs of maintenance. Integration and the management of sustainable power sources a major objective for power generation is the eradication of petroleum derivatives yet meanwhile, generating stations can eliminate discharges by joining energy generated through renewable methods like Wind and Solar with the usual coal or service stations.

Fig 2: IoT Based Power generation

IoT provide producing station with data on reach peak periods which help them plan variation between renewable sources and fossils while additionally encouraging the storage of overload energy and its utilization in peak demand periods. The output and uptime of renewable sources can likewise be effectively amplified utilizing IoT based solutions as it helps the creation esteems and in general soundness of sustainable sources irrespective of their area. Business of action and decentralization IoT are quickly prompting energy decentralization. It is at the core of a few new business of action which are making ready for commercialization of small and medium scale sustainable power source solutions. From pay as you use power grid solar system powering homes in creating nations.

3. IoT Based Power Transmission

The monitor of power transmission system was performing physically. Periodic visits were led to check the tools status. In contrast to generation, transmission systems and distribution system is generally spread over a large area. This stance great challenge for manual watching as towers and lines are situated in remote zones. IoT based online checking system for transmission towers gives progressively robust and reliable methods. The pinnacle faces harms because of numerous elements, for example, violent wind, rainstorm, tremor, against the law construction and theft which may prompt collapsing of the tower. Tilt, vibration, climate sensors and cameras installed on towers can transmit correct status of tower information to the official [6]. The online based checking of power transmission line encourages early identification of flaws and their resolution. Conductor temperature and wind influence can be observed to keep a checking the line execution and status. Likewise, IoT based observing of electrical parameters at each tower utilizing power analysis will officials the authorities to distinguish if there's a greater than predictable loss of energy. More prominent loss of energy may imply theft of power and subsequently the officials can act in like manner.

4. IoT Based Power Distribution

The specialists can distribute power all the more capably in this IoT supported smart grid. Smart energy meters send the use information to the cloud. The authorities have total data with respect to the load consumption in every area and at every moment of time. They can rearrange their scheduling plans dependent on load need and make the circulation effective and optimized. This will improve consistency and cost efficiency. There is a lot of human exertion required in physically proceeding to keep a mind generation, transmission or distribution apparatus. This human work is diminished with use of IoT devices and systems. The internet checking helps in find the tool requiring consideration and its area. This enables the experts in state support, to staff situating for watching, hardware status reports and climate observing. With the help of IoT, the system can distinguish faults immediately and make a right move. A smart distribution grid may have temperature, dampness, noise sensors for checking of circulation grid. Tower tilt sensors are likewise used to let know the specialists about tilt status of towers and to make a move for preservation on the off-chance that it has arrived at a specific tilt angle.

5. IoT Based Power Consumption

The power from distribution hub is distributed to customers, both housing and industrial. Role of IoT in making the consumer utilization intelligent is discussed. Power utilization smart energy meters utilizing IoT: Traditionally, it required human effort to read power utilization at explicit interims from energy meter at consumer premises. It has disservices, for example, extra cost of meter reader, inclined to human mistake and safety issues because of meters being installed inside consumer's premises.

Smart Energy meters are essential element of the SG. They send the power consumption information to the cloud. Both the authorities just as the user can keep a check of the power consumed in real time through a web or mobile application interface [8]. The user can likewise perform analytics to predict the month-to-month bill dependent on his use information. This IoT based Advanced Monitoring Infrastructure is progressively dependable, strong, efficient and cost effective.

Fig 3: Different applications using power consumption based on IoT

Power consumption smart cities utilizing IoT based systems are a key feature in current days smart cities. A smart city may have the subsequent systems Smart streets lights IoT based smart street lighting can have parts, for example, LDR (Light Dependent Resistor), Relays, Passive Infrared (PIR) sensor and real time clock [9]. The components associate with a control unit which is connected with a central manage unit over the internet. All the street lights are checked on the online and can be turned on/off over the internet. Light Dependent Resistor changes obstruction based on light and consequently, can be utilized to modify brightness of lighting dependent on climate condition. Water Supply and Storage Distance estimating sensors can detect the level of water in the capacity tank. The water stage is observed real time and valves can be closed at a specific required level. Rate flow sensor checks if there's any leakage between two progressive sensors. The rate flow is checked on the online and any kind of leakage or theft is reported. Surveillance IoT based surveillance systems are being checked real time by the authorities remotely. In case of accident or other incidents, the caught video can be dissected utilizing picture handling methods and essential action can be initiated. Power consumption home and building automation system utilizing IoT plays a main role in modern home and house automation systems. The system consists of Intelligent lighting system Passive Infrared sensors are utilized to monitor movement in the room and the lights are turned off consequently if there is no growth for an exact period of time.

The light switch is connected with the internet and the end user can remotely monitoring the status of lights in each room and can turn on or off the lights from the web or application interface itself. Insightful appliances the current days appliances, for example, TV, washing machine, Refrigerator, and air conditioner and so on are connected with the internet consequently making them smart. It is presently possible to turn on the AC and set it to an ideal temperature over the internet five minutes before you arrive at the home from work. Sensors, for example, control analyzers can be installing at the appliance attachment to measure the power consumed by every appliance. The sensor can be linked with a control unit which will go about asa gateway and transfer sensor information to the cloud.

In this way, the end user can remotely monitor and control every appliance, elevator checking system there are different unit in a same time. The control unit of the elevator can be associated with the internet and subsequently empower the end consumer to check the status of the every one of the lifts in a building on a web or application interface in real time. Safety and security gas and smoke sensors are utilized to detect fire and raise an alert. The internet associated control unit can consequently inform the closest firefighter unit through message or automated mail over the internet for fear that sensors irritated a particular threshold value. IoT based surveillance systems are using for real time wireless checking of home.

6. Security Issues and Challenges IoT based Smart Grid

The IoT based SG will face a few security issues as a cyber physical system, These security or protection challenges and issues could the quick organization and adoption by users of the IoT based SG. From now on, we brief explain the majority significant security challenges and issues looked on the IoT based SG. Authentications and manage access issues since a various device could be checked and arranged wireless, for example field sent sensors, actuators and smart meters in sharing substations, an attacker or even an irate representative, could attempt to gain an unofficial access right, to control them, in this manner harmful physical resources sent to energy outages [2]. Security and privacy issues in smart appliances in houses and smart meters could inform over the power utilization.

Their produced well grained information could harm the protection of the end user, by uncovering data about their habits, dinner times, sleeping and wake up so on., if they are in or away from house, if they are on vacation, etc. Eavesdropping Since a device on the IoT-based SG conveys, often utilizing public correspondence infrastructure, an attackers can simply have access to their information. An attacker simply knows the power utilization of houses. Data altering a hacker can change modified information, for example, dynamic costs sent prior to peak period, creation them most reduced costs. as a result, this could make households rising their utilization charging e-vehicles, and etc. Rather than reducing them, in this manner bringing about overloaded power network. Impersonation and uniqueness spoofing this hacker aims communicate on behalf of a legitimate thing in an unapproved way, by utilizing its character [3]. A hacker could spoof the identity of somebody's smart meter, so as to make it paying for its power utilization. Compromise and malicious code since objects of the SG are computation and correspondence empowered, they are target to compromising physically or wireless.

Since they run various software using, they could be focus of different software virus code or malicious code infected in order to control and changes them ex, focusing on smart meters and smart apparatuses in houses. Additionally, items things with obliged sensors devices, and so on. The for most tamper-resistant devices, making physical trading off a simple undertaking. When overseeing security c algorithms, conventions and policies for the IoT-based SG, a different move should be contemplated.

Mobility with cell phones and objects, for example, e-vehicles and on the technical supporters, there will be nonstop need for authentication and secure communication with evolving nearby smart meters, electrical charging points or stations, and so on [4]. The SG could span over huge regions a few urban areas or the whole country, and includes an enormous number of smart devices and objects. This will create it hard to consider adaptable security solutions, for example, key management and authentication. Deployment Since the SG could length to the entire nation, devices are sent at an enormous scale, work unattended, and could be put on remote spots with no physical perimeter protection, making them effectively available. Security arrangements ought to have the option to recognize any attempt to alter them.

Constrained Resources a various device of the smart grid, particularly those hugely deployed are resource constrained. Particular consideration should be taken when developing protection or security solutions, to be certain that their limited could accommodate the solutions. This makes applying old style security arrangements, particularly those dependent on public key cryptography test. Heterogeneity Due to the error on the assets of the devices on the SG memory, calculation, time sensitivity, energy autonomy, bandwidth, etc. Their executed conventions and correspondence stacks for non-internet protocol-based gadgets accomplishing secure or protection start to finish interchanges is a challenge task, requiring the majority often adaptation of obtainable solutions by gateways. Legacy systems already deployed devices and systems, could have an almost no help for security, since they depended generally on proprietary solutions software and hardware. Incorporating those heritage systems to the IoT based smart grid is a real time challenge, since overall, there is no genuine method to restore them with new systems, or updating them so they can support the desired security or protection solutions.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has been addressed an overview of IoT technology and its various uses in the smart grid. The smart grid as one of the major significant uses of IoT, is contemplated. SG by giving smart devices and IoT devices for example, sensors, actuators and smart meters for the checking, investigation and controlling the grid, just as network, automation and following of such devices. This understands the IoT-helped SG system which supports and improves different network functions at the generation, transmission, distribution, and usage. The perspective of applications, very less work has been done on the applications of IoT aided smart grid systems. The systems power generation, transmission, distribution and consumption. Therefore, there is a require of designing a new reference architecture for IoT-aided SG systems and consider these specific aspects in that architecture. The change towards a smart grid from the current electric grid is one of the most important decisions to meet for electric reliability, economy, efficiency and sustainability goals.

Only through a well-structured grid, efficient, reliable and the main security issues and challenges for the SG, and IoT the major required security services. Secure communication technologies and integrated intelligent decision-making capabilities associated with the structure; a Smart Grid can evolve. An integrated environment with distributed generation sources, a good transmission management system. Smart grid is the future grid which solves the problems of uni-directional data flow, power wastage, rising power demand, reliability and security in the traditional power grid. The IoT technology provides connectivity anywhere and any-time.

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